

Impact of the ocean mesoscale on ocean model biases

A first look at the eddy-rich coupled simulations

Deliverable ID	D6.1
Work Package Reference	WP6
Issue	Version 1.0
Due Date of Deliverable	31/12/2024
Submission Date	31/12/2024
Dissemination Level	PU
Lead Partner	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)
Contributors	Met Office Hadley Center (MOHC), Max-Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M), Alfred Wegner Institute (AWI), Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)
Grant Agreement No	101081383
Call ID	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02-02

ETH Zürich's contribution to EERIE is funded by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract #22.00366.

All UK Partners in EERIE are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee (grant numbers 10057890, 10049639, 10040510, 10040984).

Prepared by Delpech, Audrey Frigola, Amanda Ghosh, Rohit Goldsworth, Fraser Libera, Stephy Ortega, Pablo Roberts, Malcolm Tréguier, Anne-Marie von Storch, Jin-Song	Reviewed by EERIE coordinators	Approved by EERIE coordinators
---	--	--

Issue	Date	Description	Author
1.0	10/12/2024	First issue of the deliverable	Delpech, Audrey Frigola, Amanda Ghosh, Rohit Goldsworth, Fraser Libera, Stephy Ortega, Pablo Roberts, Malcolm Tréguier, Anne-Marie von Storch, Jin-Song

Index

Index	3
Executive Summary	5
1 Introduction	6
2 Models and Simulations	7
2.1 Characteristics of the ocean and sea ice components of the EERIE models	7
2.1.1 ICON (MPI-M)	7
2.1.2 IFS-FESOM (AWI)	7
2.1.3 HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE (MOHC)	8
2.1.4 IFS-NEMO (BSC)	8
2.1.5 Discussion	8
2.2 Datasets used in this report	11
3 Key variables	12
3.1 Sea Surface Height and Eddy Variability	12
3.1.1 Introduction	12
3.1.2 Mean SSH and Biases	13
3.1.3 Eddy variability	15
3.1.4 Summary	15
3.2 Ocean Currents	16
3.2.1 Introduction	16
3.2.2 Method	16
3.2.3 Surface velocity	18
3.2.4 Deep velocity	25
3.2.5 Summary	29
3.3 Sea Surface Temperature	29
3.3.1 Global Biases	30
3.3.2 Seasonal Cycle	32
3.3.3 Regional focus: the Western European Shelf	33
3.3.4 Summary	35
3.4 Sea Surface Salinity	35
3.4.1 Global Biases	36
3.4.2 Seasonal Cycle	38
3.4.3 Regional focus: Influence of rivers runoff on salinity	39
3.4.4 Summary	41
3.5 Sea Ice	42
3.5.1 Arctic Ocean	43
3.5.2 Southern Ocean	44
3.5.3 Summary	47
3.6 Mixed-Layer Depth	47
3.6.1 Seasonal Mixed-Layer Depth	49

3.6.2 Seasonal Biases	51
3.6.3 Summary	52
3.7 Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation	53
3.7.1 AMOC mean state and variability	55
3.7.2 Comparison with observations	57
3.7.3 Summary	59
3.8 Climate variability : El Niño Southern Oscillation	59
3.8.1 ENSO Index: Models and Reanalysis	60
3.8.2 ENSO Spatial Patterns	60
3.8.3 Summary	61
4 Discussion and Conclusion	62
5 References	64

Executive Summary

The EERIE (European Eddy-Rich Earth system models) project aims at overcoming the lack of representation of oceanic eddies in climate models by delivering eddy-rich coupled climate simulations (including ocean, atmosphere and sea ice), which include three HighResMIP-style simulations and one CMIP6-style simulation. This report constitutes a first cross-evaluation of the ocean and sea ice in EERIE simulations and a comprehensive analysis of the role of eddy-rich models in alleviating some of the known oceanic models biases, targeting eight climate relevant variables: sea surface temperature and salinity, mixed-layer depth, sea ice, sea surface height, oceanic currents, the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation and El Niño Southern Oscillation variability. Our findings suggest that eddy-rich coupled simulations considerably improve the dynamical variables (ocean currents, sea surface height and variability), in particular in the western boundary regions, which are known to be keys in the redistribution of heat at a global scale. For other variables such as sea surface temperature and salinity, the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation, mixed layer depth, if the biases are generally reduced at a global scale compared to CMIP models, they are still very much model and region dependent. No improvement has been noted for sea ice representation in eddy-rich models.

1 Introduction

The EERIE project has started to produce very ambitious coupled model simulations featuring eddy-rich ocean models, with a spatial resolution of less than 10 km. These simulations, documented in EERIE deliverable D4.1 (Robert et al., 2024), follow two different protocols: the HighReMIP protocol, with the control experiment starting in 1950, and the CMIP protocol, with a control simulation starting in 1850 (Met Office only). The model developments are extremely ambitious, notably the new ICON coupled model at MPI-M, and the coupling of FESOM and NEMO to a new version of the ECMWF atmospheric model IFS, by AWI and BSC.

The present report on the impact of resolving ocean eddies on ocean biases is written at a time when only the control simulations are available. Biases in coupled models are measured against observations, which cover the recent historical period. We did not wait for the historical simulations to be completed to carry out our analysis. We chose to perform a rapid evaluation of the control simulations, focusing on a limited number of variables, because this strategy will provide timely information for the EERIE General Assembly in January 2025, and will help design the second phase of EERIE.

This report has two objectives :

- 1) Expose strengths and weaknesses of the ocean-ice models used during the first phase of EERIE, to inform the design of the “phase 2” experiments;
- 2) Identify the most relevant processes or regions where significant advances in understanding will be enabled by the EERIE models, in order to refine the scientific agenda of EERIE WP 6.

The choice of key variables reflects the processes to be investigated in WP6, notably the role of ocean eddies in setting ocean properties, with a focus on upper ocean dynamics and the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC). The set of variables was necessarily limited to keep the analysis feasible in the few months available between the completion of the simulations and the general assembly.

We present the characteristics of the ocean and sea-ice models used in EERIE, and then the analysis of the following variables: sea surface height, current velocities, sea surface temperature and salinity, sea ice, mixed layer depth, AMOC, and a few indicators of climate variability. Perspectives for further work are presented in the last section.

2 Models and Simulations

2.1 Characteristics of the ocean and sea ice components of the EERIE models

The EERIE coupled models use three unique ocean components: ICON-Ocean, FESOM and NEMO-ORCA12. Two different configurations of the latter are used by the Met Office and BSC, coupled to the Met Office Unified atmospheric Model and to the ECMWF IFS atmospheric model, respectively. The coupled simulations are described in more detail in deliverable D4.1 (Roberts et al., 2024). We present here a brief summary of the characteristics of the ocean and sea-ice components of the coupled models, and three tables documenting the numerical choices and parameters for each model.

2.1.1 ICON (MPI-M)

ICON (“ICOsahedral Nonhydrostatic”) is the new framework for the MPI-M Earth system model, described by Hohenegger et al. (2023) and Jungclaus et al. (2022). The ocean component solves the primitive equations (hydrostatic) using conservative schemes on a grid with triangular elements and C-type staggering (Korn, 2017). The advection scheme is a vector invariant form with Perot’s mimetic reconstruction used to reconstruct vorticity and kinetic energy (Korn, 2017, 2018). The sea ice model is based on the finite element sea ice model FESIM (Danilov et al., 2015). A global configuration of ICON-O with a nominal resolution of 10km has been described in (Korn et al., 2022), and a simulation forced by ERA5 has been assessed in comparison with observations.

2.1.2 IFS-FESOM (AWI)

The ocean component is version 2.5 of FESOM (Finite Element Sea Ice Ocean Model), configured with an NG5 unstructured triangular grid and 70 depth levels. This configuration provides a minimum horizontal resolution of 5 km in eddy-rich mid- and high-latitude regions and a resolution of approximately 13 km over the tropics. It is similar to the one described in Rackow et al. (2024). The sea ice model is FESIM (Danilov et al. 2015, Korn et al. 2022). The ice dynamics are based on the Elastic-Viscous-Plastic (EVP) scheme of Hunke & Dukowicz (1997).

2.1.3 HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE (MOHC)

The model configuration used for EERIE is based on HadGEM3-CG5 (Xavier et al., 2024, *in prep.*) The ocean-ice component is based on the NEMO modelling framework version 4.04. The configuration is GOSI9 (Guiavarc'h et al., 2024). It includes the sea ice model SI3 (Sea Ice modelling Integrated Initiative, Blockley et al., 2024). This is a change relative to the HadGEM-GC3.1 model used for CMIP6 (Roberts et al., 2019) where the sea ice model was CICE5.1. Guiavarc'h et al. (2024) document large improvements of the biases in GOSI9 relative to the configuration GO6, which used version 3.6 of NEMO. The HH (high atmosphere, high ocean) resolution is as defined in Tables 1-3; a lower MM resolution (60km atmosphere, ~25km ocean) simulation is also used in some of the analysis for comparison.

2.1.4 IFS-NEMO (BSC)

This model is composed of version 4.0.7 of the ocean model component NEMO, which includes the sea ice model SI3, both running on a tripolar global orthogonal curvilinear mesh with 75 vertical levels and a horizontal resolution of $1/12^\circ$ (ORCA12), coupled to cycle 48r1 of the atmospheric model IFS configured with 137 vertical levels and a triangular-cubic-octahedral at 10 km resolution (Tco1279).

2.1.5 Discussion

The numerical choices and parameterization settings of the EERIE ocean models, listed in Tables 1 to 3, are consistent with the state of the art for eddy-rich ocean models. Regarding the vertical dimension, all models use a z^* coordinate and a second-order closure (Turbulent Kinetic Energy, TKE). The thickness of the top model level differs across models, from 1 m in NEMO to 5 m in FESOM. This may influence some climate characteristics such as sea surface temperature extremes (Wang et al., 2022). It is notable that none of the unstructured grid models uses a partial cell representation of the bathymetry, although this representation has been found to improve the representation of boundary currents and is almost universally adopted in the NEMO community (Barnier et al., 2006). Regarding the horizontal dimensions, different choices are made regarding the diffusion of tracers: diffusion is made by the numerical advection scheme in ICON, but an explicit isoneutral laplacian diffusion is added in NEMO and FESOM. It will be interesting to see if the latter choice leads to a better preservation of water mass properties along neutral surfaces. Finally, although EERIE models resolve mesoscale eddies in the tropics, their resolution is still insufficient in the polar regions. For this reason two models (ICON and HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE) have implemented a

Gent-McWilliams parameterization. The representation of boundary currents and eddies in the subpolar regions may vary across models due to these different choices.

Institution	MPI-M	AWI	Met Office	BSC
Model name	ICON	IFS-FESOM	HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE	IFS-NEMO
Ocean code version	ICON-O v2.6.6	FESOM 2.5	NEMO v4.0.4	NEMO v4.0.7
Horizontal resolution	Unstructured icosahedral grid. 5 km resolution globally.	Unstructured grid,	Tripolar grid, 1/12°. 9.2 km at the equator 4.6 km at 60°	Tripolar grid, 1/12°. 9.2 km at the equator 4.6 km at 60°
Number of vertical levels	72	70	75	75
Thickness of the top model layer	2 m	5 m	1 m	1 m
Vertical coordinate	z*	z*	z*	z*
Lateral boundary condition	No-slip	No-slip	Free slip with partial slip in Southern Ocean	Free slip
Topography representation	Full cells	Full cells	Partial cells	Partial cells
Input bathymetry	SRTM30 (Becker et al 2009)	GEBCO_2014 (Weatherall et al., 2015)	GEBCO_2021 (GEBCO Compilation Group (2021))	ORCA12 v3.3 bathymetry from MERCATOR, with some modification over lake regions.
Bathy interpolation/smoothing	Nearest neighbour interpolation	Nearest neighbour	Nearest neighbour	None
Bathymetry adjustments	Manual adjustment in straits	Manual adjustment in straits	Manual adjustment in straits	None
Time stepping method	Adam Bashford 2	Asynchronous (forward-backward) time stepping with split-explicit solver	Leap-frog scheme with Robert-Asselin filter	Leap-frog scheme with Robert-Asselin filter
Time step	5 min	5min	7.5 min	5 min
Equation of state	EOS80	EOS80	TEOS10	TEOS10
River runoff	Routed by JSBACH	Climatological runoff (Large and yeager 2009)	TRIP, fully coupled	Uncoupled climatological runoff
Ice shelves	None	None	Ice shelf basal melting (Mathiot et al., 2017)	None

Table 1: General characteristics of the EERIE ocean models.

Institution	MPI-M	AWI	Met Office	BSC
Model name	ICON	IFS-FESOM	HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE	IFS-NEMO
Lateral advection of tracers	FCT (Zalesak, 1979)	MUSCL 3rd order + FCT	TVD 4th order (Zalesak 1979)	FCT Scheme
Lateral advection of momentum	Vector invariant form (Korn, 2017, 2018)	Scalar	Vector form, 2nd order enstrophy and energy conserving	Vector form - 2nd order centered scheme
Gent-McWilliams parameterization (GM)	No	Yes, according to Ferrari et al. 2010 resolution dependent	GM with coefficient 0 at low latitudes and up to 75 m ² /s at high latitudes	No
Fox-Kemper parameterization	None	None	None	None
Lateral mixing of tracers	None	Redi isoneutral laplacian diffusion	Isonneutral Laplacian	Isonneutral Laplacian
Lateral mixing of momentum	biharmonic	biharmonic	biharmonic	biharmonic
Bottom boundary layer scheme	None	None	Advective and diffusive	Advective and diffusive
Bottom friction	Quadratic	Quadratic	Quadratic	Quadratic
Penetration of solar radiation	Exponentially decreasing in depth (Jerlov). Spatially homogeneous water type.	Shortwave penetration after CORE2 protocol using constant chlorophyll concentration of 0.1	Exponential decrease. Water type: fixed spatially uniform chlorophyll	Exponential decrease. Water type: fixed spatially uniform chlorophyll
Vertical mixing scheme (VM)	TKE (Turbulent Kinetic Energy)	TKE	TKE	TKE
VM: Vertical convection	Unstable stratification = extra TKE source.	Unstable stratification = extra TKE source	Enhanced diffusivity 10 m ² /s	Enhanced vertical diffusivity 10 m ² /s
VM: Langmuir cell parameterization	Simple Langmuir scheme based on Axell (2002)	None	Simple Langmuir scheme based on Axell (2002)	Simple Langmuir scheme based on Axell (2002)
VM: interior mixing, Double diffusion	Background mixing term	Background mixing term	Tidal mixing scheme, Simmons et al 2004	Tidal mixing scheme, Simmons et al 2004
Fox-Kemper parameterization	None	None	None	None

Table 2: Ocean advection schemes and parametrizations in the EERIE models.

Institution	MPI-M	AWI	Met Office	BSC
Model name	ICON	IFS-FESOM	HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE	IFS-NEMO
Sea ice model	FESIM	FESIM	SI ³	SI ³
Dynamics	FESIM EVP, interpolation from B-grid to C-grid	FESIM EVP, on A-grid	EVP rheology scheme	EVP rheology scheme
Thermodynamics	From MPI-OM	IFS thermodynamics with 1.5m ice thickness assumption	SI ³ (Blockley et al 2024)	SI ³
Ice categories for dynamics	1	1	5	5
Ice categories for thermodynamics	1 ice, 1 snow	1 ice, 1 snow	4 layers of ice, 1 snow	4 layers of ice, 1 snow
Iceberg representation	None	None	Freshwater iceberg climatology	None

Table 3: General characteristics of the sea ice models and interactions with land ice

2.2 Datasets used in this report

For this intercomparison, we have used the last period of 20 years available for the control experiment.

- Met Office: control-1850 CMIP6 simulation, year number 2031-2050;
- AWI: control-1950 HighREsMIP simulation, year number 1950-1969;
- MPI: control-1950 HighREsMIP simulation (second EERIE experiment), year number 1991-2011

For the BSC model, unfortunately, the control experiment was not yet available at the time of this writing. Therefore we used the last 20 years of the spin up (performed under 1950 conditions), year number 1980-1999.

The first three datasets have been interpolated from the high resolution native grid onto a common regular 1/4° grid, using bilinear interpolation. The BSC model data have been saved on a regular 1° grid (this being the standard procedure during model spin-up). All datasets have been gathered at DKRZ and integrated into the EERIE catalog to facilitate the joint analysis of the models.

Note that all the simulations are aimed at simulating a past climate (1850 or 1950), while the observations we use are generally much closer to the present day. This should be remembered when looking at model biases in the analyses below.

3 Key variables

We investigate in the following sections the ability of the EERIE models to accurately represent key oceanic and climate relevant variables and comment on the improvement of eddy-rich models compared to state-of-the-art low resolution CMIP6 models.

3.1 Sea Surface Height and Eddy Variability

3.1.1 Introduction

Figure 1: From Lyu et al. 2020 (a) Observed mean SSH derived from Satellite and drifter trajectories (Maximenko et al., 2009) over 1992–2012; differences of the (b) CMIP6 and (c) CMIP5 multimodel-averaged mean SSH over 1986–2005 from the observed mean dynamic topography; and (d) differences between the mean SSH from CMIP6 and CMIP5. Stippling in lower panels indicates where the difference between CMIP6 and CMIP5 is statistically significant at the 95% confidence level based on the two-sample t test.

The ocean dynamic sea level, commonly referred to as sea surface height (SSH) is influenced by both ocean density and circulation, and it is defined as the local height of the sea surface above the geoid, with a global mean of zero (Gregory et al., 2019).

A comprehensive analysis of how the SSH is simulated in the climate models that participated in previous coupled model intercomparison projects (CMIPs) is provided in Lyu et al. (2020). Figure 1 shows an excerpt from that article depicting the mean sea surface height in the observations and the bias in

CMIP6 models as well as in the CMIP5 models (Figure 1b, c), and the difference between them (Figure 1d).

The upper-ocean general circulation is intimately linked to mean sea level through geostrophic balance. This relationship manifests as relatively elevated sea levels within subtropical gyres and comparatively lower levels in subpolar gyres (Figure 1a).

While climate models generally demonstrate proficiency in simulating mean sea level, notable regional biases persist in the simulations. Both the CMIP5 and CMIP6 multimodel ensemble averages exhibit remarkably similar patterns of bias when compared to observational data (Figure 1b, c). The mean sea level over the equatorial band (2°S – 2°N) reveals discrepancies between observational data and model simulations across individual ocean basins. Both CMIP5 and CMIP6 models exhibit a high bias in mean sea level in the western and eastern tropical Pacific, while showing a low bias in the central tropical Pacific ($\sim 140^{\circ}\text{E}$ – 150°W) compared to observations (Figure 1b, c). These biases result in a larger sea level gradient between the western boundary and the central tropical Pacific, and a smaller gradient between the eastern boundary and the central tropical Pacific than observed. In the western boundary current regions of the North Pacific and North Atlantic, mean sea level biases suggest weaker meridional gradients in model simulations, indicating that the simulated Kuroshio Extension and Gulf Stream may be less pronounced than observed. Conversely, positive mean sea level biases in the Southern Hemisphere midlatitude band suggest stronger subtropical ocean gyres.

3.1.2 Mean SSH and Biases

The IFS-NEMO data have been archived at 1° resolution and with monthly SSH mean only, which made it impossible to use this model to assess SSH variability. Here we use IFS-FESOM, ICON and the HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE model at two resolutions: HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE-HH ($1/12^{\circ}$ in the ocean) and HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE-MM ($1/4^{\circ}$ in the ocean). For these EERIE models, we observe an overall improvement in the representation of global SSH (Figure 2). The spatial pattern of the SSH climatology closely resembles that of the multi-satellite altimetry data of absolute dynamic topography from AVISO (Pujol et.al. 2016). Furthermore, the systematic SSH bias in CMIP models over the tropical Pacific has been eliminated (Figure 3). Similarly, the SSH bias over the northwestern Indian Ocean has been removed, and the bias associated with a weak Kuroshio Current has been resolved in these eddy-rich coupled simulations.

Examining individual models, IFS-FESOM exhibits the strongest negative anomalies from the Gulf Stream to the subpolar gyre region. This suggests a stronger western-to-central subpolar gyre and a potentially overly zonal North Atlantic Current (Figure 3a). Conversely, the ICON model displays

weaker gyre circulations at mid to high latitudes (Figure 3b) and higher positive bias over the Kuroshio Current region compared to other models.

Figure 2: SSH mean from a) the AVISO data (1993-2021) and from the control simulation with 1950 radiative forcing for b) IFS-FESOM, c) ICON and with 1850 radiative forcing for d) HadGEM3-GC5-HH and e) HadGEM3-GC5-MM. The units are in meters.

Comparing biases in the HadGEM3-GC5 model across medium and high resolutions, we find that the overall bias pattern is similar. However, the high-resolution version shows a reduced amplitude of bias, particularly in the subpolar regions (Figure 3c, d).

Figure 3: Bias in mean SSH relative to AVISO data (1993-2021) in a) IFS-FESOM b) ICON and in c) HadGEM3-GC5-HH and d) HadGEM3-GC5-MM. The units are in meters.

3.1.3 Eddy variability

The daily SSH variability represents the ocean mesoscale eddy activity and highlights the regions of higher ocean eddy activity. Figure 4 shows the standard deviation of the daily SSH in IFS-FESOM and ICON (the other EERIE models did not have daily SSH output at the time of this report) and in the AVISO product. We find that both models are able to represent the eddy-rich regions well. However, ICON in general shows a positive bias throughout the ocean, potentially indicating a more noisy ocean surface, whose reason is still under investigation. Furthermore, the simulated eddy activity over the Gulf stream region shows differences from what has been observed: The SSH standard deviation is in general weaker and stretched more zonally in the models compared to AVISO.

Figure 4: The daily SSH standard deviation from a) the AVISO data (1993-2021) and the same climatology from the control simulation with 1950 radiative forcing in b) IFS-FESOM c) ICON. The units are in meters.

3.1.4 Summary

The analysis of the SSH in EERIE climate models highlights significant advancements over previous CMIP5 and CMIP6 simulations. SSH biases, prevalent in earlier models – such as large biases in the western and eastern tropical Pacific, low biases in the central tropical Pacific, and weaker Kuroshio Extension and Gulf Stream gradients – have been substantially mitigated in EERIE models. Improvements include the elimination of biases in the tropical Pacific and northwestern Indian Ocean, and better representation of the Kuroshio Current. Among individual models, IFS-FESOM displays strong subpolar gyres but overly zonal currents, ICON shows weaker gyre circulation with higher positive biases, and HadGEM3-GC5 demonstrates reduced bias at higher resolutions. Daily SSH variability analysis indicates effective mesoscale eddy representation, though ICON exhibits a global positive bias and both ICON and IFS-FESOM still show limitations in the representation of the Gulf Stream and North Atlantic drift variability. Overall, the EERIE models provide a marked enhancement in SSH simulation accuracy, reflecting improved global and regional dynamics.

3.2 Ocean Currents

3.2.1 Introduction

Ocean velocity is a prognostic variable in each of the models contributing to EERIE making it, computationally speaking, a variable of key importance. Physically speaking, the ocean velocity is responsible for redistributing heat and salt within the ocean. Poorly modelled ocean currents have been linked to anomalous ocean heat transports (Si et al., 2023) and reduced ocean warming under climate change scenarios (Saba et al., 2015), for example. A key problem for all ocean models (both coupled and uncoupled) is that at low resolutions they are unable to properly resolve the energetic Western boundary currents which close the oceanic gyre circulations (Hewitt et al., 2020). These currents are responsible for large transports of heat, salt and mass which are of climatic importance (Palter, 2015; Ichikawa & Chaen, 2000). As models move towards eddy resolving resolutions it is expected that characteristics of the modelled boundary currents such as their speed and width will improve, as will their variability and pathways (Hewitt et al. 2020).

In this section, we will examine velocity biases at the surface and at 1,000 m depth in the four different EERIE models relative to observations. In the deep ocean we will demonstrate that model biases are similar to those found when examining different gridded datasets. In the surface ocean we will find some promising results, such as the resolution of currents that are too fine-scale to exist in coarse gridded data products; however, we will also identify biases in the location of boundary current separations and in the equatorial region.

3.2.2 Method

The five models we have velocity data available for are the HadGEM3-GC5-MM and HadGEM3-GC5-HH models (Met Office), hereafter GC5-MM and GC5-HH, the IFS-FESOM model (AWI), the ICON model (MPI-M), and the IFS-NEMO model (BSC). For each model we take 20 years of monthly data and conservatively interpolate it onto a regular 0.25° latitude-longitude grid. The exception to this procedure is the IFS-NEMO model, where we only have five full years of data available on a 1° grid. We then temporally average the data to produce a climatology of the currents. The current speeds and directions are calculated from the climatology. We consider speed rather than the separate zonal and meridional components of velocity as the post-processing required to remap the velocity from the model grid to a lat-lon grid has not yet been performed on the GC5 models. The directions of the time mean currents are calculated for the IFS-FESOM and ICON models. Due to the coarseness of the regridded IFS-NEMO model outputs, in what follows, we exclude the model from any regional analysis and do not calculate model biases.

To assess the biases we will use four different observationally derived data products. In the surface ocean, we use velocities from the OSCAR v2.0 (Ocean Surface Currents Analyses Real-time) (ESR,

2022) and Laurindo v3.10 (Laurindo et al., 2017, Laurindo et al., 2023) datasets. OSCAR uses satellite observations of sea surface height and sea surface temperature, and ERA5 reanalysis wind speeds to drive a simplified model of the surface mixed layer (Bonjean & Lagerloef, 2002; Dohan, 2021). The product is provided as velocities on a 0.25° grid and averaged over the first 30 m of the Ocean’s surface. We construct a climatology by time averaging the dataset from 1993 to 2013. The Laurindo dataset (Laurindo et al., 2023) assimilates displacement data from the 15 m global drifter program. Corrections are made for the slip of undrogued drifters and both seasonal and eddying contributions to the velocity vector are removed. The dataset is provided as a monthly climatology of velocity averaged over the top 15 m of the Ocean’s surface on a 0.25° grid. The time mean of the monthly data is taken to produce an annual climatology. Taken together the Laurindo and OSCAR data products provide a good way to assess biases in the models as they are derived from different data sources and make different assumptions. The Laurindo dataset for instance is less affected by the breakdown of geostrophic balance at the equator.

To assess model biases in the deep ocean (at 1,000 m) we use two products derived from ARGO displacement data: the G-YoMaHa (Katsumata & Yoshinari, 2010; Katsumata, 2011) and the ANDRO (Ollitrault et al., 2024; Ollitrault & Rannau, 2013) products. Both products are provided on a 0.25° grid as a single year velocity climatology. (Note that the G-YoMaHa product is distinct from the YoMaHa’07 product of Lebedev et al. (2007).)

Table 4: Globally averaged mean and RMS biases of data products.

Model ^a	Surface 15 m relative to Laurindo		Surface 30 m relative to OSCAR		Deep (1,000 m) relative to ANDRO	
	Mean bias (cm s ⁻¹)	RMS bias (cm s ⁻¹)	Mean bias (cm s ⁻¹)	RMS bias (cm s ⁻¹)	Mean bias (cm s ⁻¹)	RMS bias (cm s ⁻¹)
GC5-MM	(-2.37 ^b)	(7.64 ^b)	–	–	0.06	1.77
GC5-HH	-2.70	6.93	-0.06	6.39	0.19	1.83
IFS-FESOM	-0.55	7.83	2.76	8.39	-0.12	2.19
ICON	-1.73	8.98	0.47	7.60	0.16	1.72
OSCAR	(-3.60 ^c)	(7.13 ^c)	–	–	–	–
G-YoMaHa	–	–	–	–	-0.59	1.97

^aThe IFS-NEMO data is provided on a coarser grid than the observational data products used to calculate biases, so the model is not included in this table.

^bThe GC5-MM data was provided only at the surface rather than averaged over the surface 15 m, so the numbers stated here are not strictly comparable.

^cOSCAR velocities are averaged over the surface 30 m rather than surface 15 m, so the numbers stated here are not strictly comparable.

3.2.3 Surface velocity

In Figure 5 we show the sea surface velocity in each of the EERIE models alongside the OSCAR and Laurindo observational products. At first glance, the models appear to do a reasonable job at capturing the large-scale features of the ocean velocity field. All models have enhanced currents in the Southern Ocean, boundary current regions and off the equator. Upon close inspection we can begin to identify deficiencies – the currents in the equatorial Pacific are too strong in both the IFS-FESOM and ICON models, whilst the currents in the equatorial Indian Ocean seem to be too weak in both of the GC5 models and the IFS-NEMO model.

In Figures 6 and 7 we average the model velocities in GC5-HH, ICON, and IFS-FESOM over the surface 15 m and surface 30 m of the ocean and then subtract the Laurindo and OSCAR climatologies to produce plots showing the biases in the models explicitly. (The required data was unavailable for the GC5-MM and IFS-NEMO models, hence their omission from these plots.) The bias plots highlight excessive current speeds in the Tropical Pacific in all the models. The magnitude of the bias is similar in size to the biases Si et al. (2023) found contributed to sea surface temperature biases of up to 2°C in the same region.

In Figure 5, a large-scale bias in the sea-surface velocity is apparent in the ICON model, with the sea surface velocities appearing large within the wind driven gyres compared to the observational products. Making such comparisons is not strictly speaking fair as the observational products have been averaged over the surface 15 m and 30 m of the ocean for the Laurindo and OSCAR products respectively. In Figures 6 and 7 we perform this averaging, and the positive bias we may expect to see is absent, with the biases in ICON being largely comparable with those in GC5-HH and IFS-FESOM.

Surface currents

Figure 5: Surface currents in each (a - e) model and (f - g) observational product. Bracketed numbers in the title indicate the depth of the model level, or, in the case of the observations, the depth over which the velocities have been averaged. Note the currents are averaged over different vertical depth ranges so care should be taken when interpreting differences.

0 m to 15 m averaged current bias

Figure 6: (a - b) Biases in the currents averaged over the surface 15 m of the ocean relative to the Laurindo data product. (c) The average current speed in the surface 15 m of the ocean from the Laurindo data product.

In Table 4 we show the globally averaged bias and the globally averaged root mean square bias of the models relative to different data products. (We also calculate the bias of the OSCAR dataset and GC5-MM models relative to the Laurindo dataset, although these numbers aren't strictly comparable because of the vertical averaging that is performed.) We see that the mean and root mean square biases for each of the models is similar to the discrepancies in the two data products. Although a crude metric, this suggests the models are performing well compared to observational uncertainties.

Having taken a global view, we will now assess how the models perform in the representation of currents in three important boundary current regions: the Gulf Stream, the Kuroshio and the Labrador Sea.

0 m to 30 m averaged current bias

Figure 7: (a - b) Biases in the currents averaged over the surface 30 m of the ocean relative to the OSCAR data product. (c) The average current speed in the surface 30 m of the ocean from the OSCAR data product.

All models reproduce the approximate speed and pathway of the Gulf Stream (Figure 8). The GC5-HH model does the best job of reproducing the latitude of the Gulf Stream's separation from the East Coast of North America. Conversely, the GC5-MM and ICON models have the Gulf stream separating around a degree or so too far North, as does IFS-FESOM (if to a lesser extent). Our understanding of the mechanism by which the Gulf Stream separates is incomplete; however, it has been suggested that increasing resolution to at least $1/10^\circ$ (Chassignet & Marshall, 2008) and accurately resolving the bathymetry (Schoonover et al., 2016; Ezer, 2016) can help in this regard.

Figure 8: Surface current speeds in the (a - d) models and (e - f) observations in the Gulf Stream western boundary current system.

The GC5 models employ partial cell discretisation in the vertical which may help in representing the bathymetry in the GC5-HH model: neither the ICON nor IFS-FESOM configurations used here employ such a discretisation. Performing a more extensive vorticity budget analysis similar to that of Ezer (2016) and comparing runs of the ICON and IFS-FESOM models with partial cell discretizations turned on may help in confirming this hypothesis. We suggest the poor separation in the GC5-MM model arises from its comparatively low resolution. Westward of around 60°W we see a reduction in the modelled current speeds which is greater than the reduction seen in the observations. The position of the Gulf Stream extension is best represented in the IFS-FESOM model, and reasonably well represented in the GC5-HH and ICON models. In the GC5-MM model the extension ends up too far North.

Figure 9: Surface current speeds in the (a - d) models and (e - f) observations in the Kuroshio western boundary current system.

The Kuroshio separation is well represented in the GC5-HH and IFS-FESOM models (Figure 9). In the ICON model, the separation occurs too far north by over 5° – it is plausible that this issue has a similar root cause to the bias in the Gulf Stream separation latitude, and a more detailed study of the problem is required. It is interesting to note that in the Kuroshio region, we also see sea surface temperature biases of up to 5°C in the ICON model (Figure 15c). The separation of the Kuroshio in the GC5-MM model occurs too far south and post separation the flow does not meander as is seen in the observations, but rather remains zonal. The Kuroshio extension (the zonal post separation pathway of the Kuroshio) is known to have two states – an unstable state in which the extension appears broad and meanders weakly, and a stable state in which the current is more well defined and meanders (Wang & Pierano, 2020). Transitions between the two states are associated with decadal

timescales (Taguchi et al., 2007). Due to the shortness of the time-period considered (only twenty years) it may be that the GC5-MM simulation happens to be in an unstable state. It could equally be that eddy activity in the region is subdued in what is a comparatively coarse resolution model.

In the high latitudes, the Rossby deformation radius becomes similar to the grid-spacing of the models under analysis (~10 km) (Chelton et al., 1998), and thus we expect the mesoscale in our models to become less energetic. The limitations of the GC5-MM model's resolution become quite apparent in the broadness and diffuseness of the Labrador Current (Figure 10a) (the Current rimming the Labrador Sea). It is, however, promising to see that both the ICON model and GC5-HH models begin to resolve two boundary currents around the East Coast of Greenland – on the coastal side the East Greenland Coastal Current and offshore the East Greenland Current (Figure 10b, d) (Talley et al., 2011a, 2011b; Danialt et al., 2011; Le Bras et al., 2018). The coastal current is so narrow that it is either absent or has artificially merged with the East Greenland Current in the OSCAR and Laurindo observational datasets.

Sub-polar North Atlantic surface speeds

Figure 10: Surface current speeds in the (a - d) models and (e - f) observations in the Subpolar North Atlantic boundary current systems.

3.2.4 Deep velocity

We now examine the velocity in the deep ocean, which we take here to be the velocity at the model level closest to 1,000 m. Figure 11 shows the deep velocities for each of the models and two Argo derived, gridded data products. All five models contain fast deep currents in the Southern Ocean and in the western boundary regions as is seen in the observational products. Like with the surface velocity, both the IFS-FESOM and ICON models have strong biases on the western boundary of the Equatorial Pacific Ocean. Unlike with the surface currents there are clear differences between the two data products being used: the G-YoMaHa dataset shows the current field to be smoother than the ANDRO dataset and boundary current velocities are in places less intense. (This is shown especially clearly in Figure 13.) For the GC5, IFS-FESOM and ICON models, the globally averaged bias relative to the ANDRO dataset is smaller than the globally averaged difference between the G-YoMaHa and ANDRO datasets. Similarly, the root mean square model biases are smaller than the observational bias for the GC5 and ICON models (Table 4). This suggests that the models are doing a good job of resolving the deep ocean.

Figure 12 shows the directions of the time mean deep currents in the IFS-FESOM and ICON models, and both the G-YoMaHa and ANDRO observational products. Around $\pm 30^\circ\text{N}$ of the equator, zonal jets (alternating bands of eastward and westward flowing currents) are visible in the models. These features are virtually absent in the G-YoMaHa data product, and although some jets are visible in the ANDRO data product, they appear to lack the zonal continuity and sharpness seen in the models, possibly as a result of spatial aliasing. These jets are known to be ubiquitous and robust features in the global ocean (e.g., Maximenko et al., 2005; Richards et al., 2006; van Sebille et al., 2011; Cravatte et al., 2012; Ollitrault and Colin de Verdière 2014; Ménesguen et al., 2019), and are important for the global ocean circulation as they can transport tracers, such as oxygen across ocean basins (Delpech et al., 2020). Some early theoretical studies (Gill 1974, Rhines 1975) have outlined a mechanism for their formation which have been later investigated in the deep ocean (Delpech et al., 2021; Delpech 2021).

Deep current speed

Figure 11: Deep (1,000 m) currents in each (a - e) model and (f - g) observational product.

Figure 12: Direction of the time averaged deep (1,000 m) currents in (a) IFS-FESOM, (b) ICON, (c) G-YoMaHa and (d) ANDRO data products. Direction is expressed in ° relative to true north.

In Figure 13 we zoom in on the Subpolar North Atlantic deep boundary current system. We see very large differences between the models and the observational products, and even between the observational products themselves. The observational products give a rough indication of boundary current pathways; however, they are of little help in assessing the realism of the fine-scale features of the boundary currents (e.g. in the splitting of the deep Labrador Current). In the surface ocean the surface limb of the Labrador Current is known to split as it turns westwards away from the coast of Greenland. It is interesting to note that this splitting also occurs in the deep limb of the current in the GC5-HH and ICON models; however the splitting is non-existent in the lower resolution GC5-MM model and weaker in the IFS-FESOM model. (In the gridded ANDRO product, the splitting is absent; however, it does appear in the Argo float trajectories which the product is derived from Ollitrault & Colin de Verdière, 2014.) It seems plausible that models that better resolve the bathymetry in this area will feature more realistic pathways of both the Labrador Current's surface and deep limbs.

Sub-polar North Atlantic deep speeds

Figure 13: Deep (1,000 m) current speeds in the (a - d) models and (e - f) observations in the Subpolar North Atlantic boundary current systems.

3.2.5 Summary

When looked at as a globally integrated metric, the mean biases and RMS biases of current speed in the EERIE models are small, and compare well with the differences between different observational products. This is true of both the surface and the deep ocean.

In the surface ocean, there exist problems in the currents of the equatorial regions, particularly the western side of the equatorial Pacific. The modelled western boundary currents compare well to observations; however, problems with the separation of the Gulf Stream and Kuroshio are found in the ICON model and to a lesser extent in the IFS-FESOM and GC5-MM model. We hypothesise that the problems in ICON and IFS-FESOM could be related to the bathymetry and that using a partial cell discretisation may correct the biases (Ezer, 2016), and that in the case of the GC5-MM model we suspect the biases are related to resolution (Chassignet & Marshall, 2008). In the subpolar North Atlantic the ICON and GC5-HH models begin to resolve the two separate branches of the East Greenland current system, which are not resolved by the gridded data products we employ.

The deep ocean currents appear to have the right magnitude and approximate locations; however, the zonal jets which dominate the deep circulation in our models are absent in the G-YoMaHa product and appear to be not well resolved in the ANDRO data product. It is therefore difficult to assess the statistics of the zonal jets using the gridded products we employed here. Furthermore, the provision of the gridded datasets as single year climatologies means it isn't possible to use them for assessing variability in the statistics of the jets. When zooming in on boundary current regions the limitations of the observational products we use become even clearer, with currents appearing too broad and weak in the observations. We recommend modellers use these datasets for making large scale comparisons and find alternatives (e.g. regional datasets or ungridded Argo float trajectories) if looking at the gyre scale or smaller.

3.3 Sea Surface Temperature

Sea Surface Temperature (SST) is the temperature measured in the first few meters of the ocean. The SST directly influences the Earth's weather and climate as it controls the exchanges of heat between the ocean and the atmosphere, the formation of sea ice, the development and strengthening of tropical cyclones and extratropical storms, and is useful to detect the onset of El Niño and La Niña cycles or the thermal stress on marine ecosystems.

An accurate representation of SST in climate models is therefore key to the reliability of future climate projections. However, despite improved model performances, climate models still suffer from strong SST biases in many regions (Eyring et al., 2021). Warm SST biases are generally

observed in most climate models in the Eastern upwelling regions (along the Benguela, the Peru-Chile coast and the Southern California), in the Southern Ocean along the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) and in the Western boundary currents (Gulf Stream and Kuroshio). Cold SST biases are generally observed in the Atlantic Northwestern corner and in the North Pacific Subtropical gyre (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Figure 9.3 of the AR6 WG1 IPCC report (Fox-Kemper et al., 2021) showing the multi-model mean bias in the CMIP (left) and HighResMIP (right) simulations.

In this report, we evaluate the representation of the SST in the EERIE models against two observational datasets: EN4, which is an objective analysis of monthly in-situ temperature at 1° from 1950 to present (Good et al., 2013) and ESA-CCI (Climate Change Initiative), which provides SST observed from space radiometers (infrared and microwaves) at a daily frequency and 0.05° spatial resolution from 1980 to present (Embury et al., 2024). It is worth noting that when an insufficient number of profiles is available, EN4 is relaxed to a climatological mean. In the following the Met Office model refers to the HH resolution model (HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE-HH).

3.3.1 Global Biases

The mean SST generally decreases poleward with sharp gradients found within the Western Boundaries Currents (Gulf Stream and Kuroshio) and cold SST spatial anomalies found in the upwelling along the Equator in the Pacific and Atlantic Ocean and in the Eastern Boundary regions: Benguela, Senegal, Peru-Chile and California (Figure 15a). The two observational datasets, although coming from different sources of measurements, are in good agreement (Figure 15b), with a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 0.38°C (Table 5). The most noticeable difference is very localized in

the Hudson Bay and Baffin Sea. Some larger differences are also found in the Western Boundary Currents, possibly due to the difference in the resolution of the products.

The biases relative to the observations in the EERIE models are quite different from one model to another. Apart from IFS-NEMO (BSC model), where a cold bias is found almost all over the Globe (Figure 15f), models tend to have a warm bias in the Southern Ocean (Figure 15c-e), as also observed in the CMIP6 multi-model bias (Figure 14a).

Figure 15: (a) Mean Sea Surface Temperature (1980-1999) from ESA-CCI, (b-f) Bias of the mean temperature for (b) EN4 (1950-1969) and (c-f) the EERIE models (last 20 years of control simulation) relative to ESA-CCI.

Warm biases are found in the Benguela upwelling system, except for the Met Office model, and to a lesser extent in the other upwelling systems. The Northwestern corner of the Atlantic is also found too cold in the EERIE models, except for the Met Office model. Although most of these biases seem reduced compared to the CMIP6 multi-model mean, they seem to be amplified in the MPI model, which has the largest RMSE: 1.3°C compared to 0.65°C–0.99°C for the other models (Table 5). The MPI model also has very strong warm biases in the Kuroshio and the Arctic Ocean, and a strong cold bias in the Equatorial Pacific.

3.3.2 Seasonal Cycle

In addition to the mean SST, the seasonal cycle of the SST is also key to the climate system. All EERIE models represent the key features of the seasonal cycle amplitude: a stronger signal in the Northern Hemisphere, especially in the Western Boundary Currents, in the coastal European, in the Mediterranean and Japan and China Seas (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Amplitude of the seasonal cycle (defined as the absolute value of the difference between the January-February-March mean and the July-August-September mean) in (a-b) the observations and (c-f) the EERIE models.

The AWI model stands out with a too large amplitude in both hemispheres, and especially around Antarctica (Figure 16d), which is not in the observations (Figure 16a, b). It is to note however, that the observations do not agree well with each other, with a relative averaged bias of 0.96, which is on the same order of magnitude as the averaged biases of the EERIE models relative to the observations (Table 5).

Table 5: Global average of mean temperature, seasonal cycle amplitude, Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) relative to the different observation products.

	MPI (ICON)	AWI (FESOM)	Met Office (NEMO)	BSC (NEMO)	EN4 (in-situ)	ESA-CCI (satellite)
Mean Temperature [°C]	9.2	9.0	9.3	8.2	8.9	9.0
Bias relative to EN4 [°C]	1.2	0.70	0.68	1.0	–	0.38
Bias relative to ESA-CCI [°C]	1.3	0.70	0.65	0.99	0.38	–
Amplitude of Seasonal cycle [°C]	2.4	2.8	2.4	1.8	1.8	2.2
Bias relative to EN4 [°C]	1.5	1.7	1.1	0.2	–	0.96
Bias relative to ESA-CCI [°C]	1.2	1.3	0.67	0.96	0.96	–

3.3.3 Regional focus: the Western European Shelf

Since one of the objectives of moving towards high-resolution climate modelling is not only to improve the representation of the state of the climate globally, but also to downscale climate information at a local scale where climate adaptation strategies are decided, it is interesting to evaluate the performance of such models at a regional scale. Here we evaluate the SST over the Western European Shelf.

The SST biases are surprisingly very low over the continental Shelf compared to the Northwestern part of the domain where a persistent warm bias is found across all models and seasons (Figure 17, 18, 19). The winter biases are almost everywhere below 0.5°C (Figure 17a), but it is interesting to see that this is because of contrasting signals in the different models. MPI model has a warm bias over most of the Northwestern continental shelf (Figure 18a), reaching very strong values up to 3°C and more along the German and Danish North Sea coasts, while the AWI model has a cold bias over most of the shelf (Figure 18b) and the Met Office model has a reduced bias in this region.

Figure 17: Multi-model mean of the biases relative to ESA-CCI in (a) Winter and (b) Summer. The isobaths at 200m, 400m and 100m are represented as solid contour lines and delimitate the continental Shelf from the abyssal Plains. Regions where the absolute value of the mean bias is < 0.5°C are hatched.

The Summer biases however are very consistent from one model to another, with warm biases being located in the French Brittany region and along the French Channel coast, in the Irish Sea and along

the Great Britain Eastern coast, and along the continental slope offshore the French Brittany (Figure 17b, 19a-c).

Figure 18: Winter biases relative to ESA-CCI for some of the EERIE models. The isobaths at 200m, 400m and 100m are represented as solid contour lines and delimitate the continental Shelf from the abyssal Plains. Regions where the absolute value of the mean bias is $< 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ are hatched.

These warm summer biases can be explained by the missing tidal mixing (tides are not forced in EERIE models and in climate models in general). This mixing can be induced by the barotropic tides over very shallow seas, such as in the Ushant front at the western tip of French Brittany (Mariette and Le Cann, 1985) or the generation and breaking of tidal internal waves at sharp topographic features such as continental slopes or seamounts. This mixing will tend to destratify and cool the ocean surface layers otherwise dominated in Summer by the atmospheric net heat flux that warms up the upper layer and stratifies the ocean. We can also note the systematic warm bias at the Gibraltar Strait at the entrance of the Mediterranean Sea, which is well known to be a location of tidal internal waves generation and breaking.

Figure 19: Same as Figure 5 but for Summer.

3.3.4 Summary

In conclusion, SST biases are very unequal across EERIE models, which can be locally very strong in regions already pointed out in CMIP models: western boundary currents, upwelling systems, etc. The EERIE model biases are so different from each other that it is difficult to conclude on how eddy-rich models improve the mean SST. In addition, at a regional scale and on continental shelves, missing ocean dynamics can lead to local biases and local information should be treated with care.

3.4 Sea Surface Salinity

The ocean sea surface salinity (SSS) integrates changes in the Earth’s water cycle, and is considered a “natural rain gauge” to assess the human influence on evaporation and precipitation (Terray et al, 2012, Durack et al. 2010). SSS also plays an active role in subpolar and polar regions, where it determines the water density and the stratification (Caneill et al, 2022). Salinity anomalies are transported by ocean eddies, such as Agulhas eddies, North Brazil current or Gulf Stream rings. Biases in SSS may thus differ between the eddy-rich EERIE models and non-eddying climate models. Here we consider two observation datasets to evaluate the EERIE models: SSS from EN4 (years 1950 to 1969) and a recent dataset from ESA Climate change Initiative (CCI) for years 2011 to 2021, excluding year 2015 which has some spurious artefacts (Boutin et al., 2024).

Figure 20: Figure 3.23 of the AR6 WG1 IPCC report (Eyring et al., 2021) provides a useful reference to put the EERIE models in perspective. Negative salinity biases over the equatorial and subtropical oceans are mainly linked to biases in precipitations, for example the wrong representation of the Inter Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) in models (Eyring et al., 2021).

3.4.1 Global Biases

Figure 21 shows the mean SSS biases in the four EERIE models. These biases are smaller than the CMIP6 multimodel mean biases (Figure 20) over most of the world ocean, which is encouraging. All EERIE models have a positive salinity bias in the Arctic, similar to the CMIP6 models, but this bias is difficult to assess, especially for control simulations: Liu et al. (2022) note that there is a large spread across observational datasets of SSS in the Arctic. A fresh bias in excess of -1 PSU is found in the CMIP6 multi-model ensemble in the Southern Ocean, extending from South Africa to South of Australia (Eyring et al. 2021, their Figure 3.23; Liu et al, 2022, their figure 1h). This bias is absent or much reduced in the EERIE models, possibly due to a better representation of advective processes in the Antarctic Circumpolar current, or to an improvement in evaporation and precipitation relative to CMIP6 models.

Figure 21: a) SSS from observations (EN4) averaged for years 1950-1969. Panels b-e: Mean SSS bias in EERIE models relative to EN4. Contours -0.6 PSU (dashed) and 0.6 PSU (solid) are indicated in black.

Salinity biases are related to precipitation biases as shown in Figure 22. The precipitation biases in ICON are different from the other models, and this is reflected in the SSS. For example, ICON has a fresh bias in the Bay of Bengal, while the other EERIE models have a positive bias like the CMIP6 models (Eyring et al., 2021). This fresh bias is probably due to the positive precipitation bias in that region in ICON. Similarly, the strong fresh bias in the tropical South Atlantic in ICON seems related to the high precipitation there. However, a fresh bias is also found in ICON in the North Atlantic (Figure 21c) while the precipitation is weaker than GPCP (Figure 22c). This bias may be induced by lower evaporation related to a cold SST bias (Figure 15c), and similarly, to a lesser extent, for IFS-FESOM.

IFS-NEMO and IFS-FESOM use the same atmospheric model, and thus one would expect that SSS biases linked with atmospheric precipitation would be similar in both models. There are however notable differences. For example, IFS-FESOM has a mainly negative SSS bias over the tropics and subtropics, similar to the CMIP6 models, but IFS-NEMO has a salty bias over large regions of the Pacific. In fact, although the atmospheric component is the same, precipitation biases differ in their amplitude in the two coupled models in some regions, for example the western equatorial Atlantic (Figure 22). Overall, SSS biases in HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE are similar to IFS-NEMO and IFS-FESOM, with remarkable differences in some regions. For example, the Nordic seas appear too salty in HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE and too fresh in both IFS-ICON and IFS-FESOM.

Figure 22: a) Precipitation from GPCP (mm/day) averaged for years 1990-2009. Panels b-e: Mean precipitation bias in EERIE models relative to GPCP (mm/day).

3.4.2 Seasonal Cycle

The mean seasonal cycle has been computed for the observations and model, and the maximum SSS amplitude is shown in Figure 23. This variable has been computed in CMIP6 models by Liu et al. (2022, their Figure 9). They have found that the CMIP6 models reproduce reasonably well the observations, with some biases such as an overestimation of the seasonal amplitude in the Pacific and a spurious amplitude around 10°S due to the double ITCZ problem. Similar patterns are found in the EERIE models (Figure 23). In observations, large seasonal amplitudes are found along the coastlines where major rivers outflow, for example in the Gulf of Guinea or the Bay of Bengal. It is also the case in EERIE models. These large amplitudes seem to extend farther offshore in the ICON model (possibly due to the implementation of river runoffs in the model).

Figure 23: Amplitude of the seasonal cycle (difference between the maximum and minimum salinity over 12 months), for observation datasets (EN4 and ESA CCI) and EERIE models.

3.4.3 Regional focus: Influence of rivers runoff on salinity

In the tropical Atlantic, major rivers are sources of low salinity waters: the Amazon and Orinoco along the coast of South America, and the Niger and Congo rivers along Africa. Figure 24 shows the SSS climatology for the month of August. It is the month when the low SSS pattern originating in the Amazon plume reaches its maximum extent, and is carried eastward by the North Brazil Current (NBC) retroflexion and the North Equatorial Countercurrent (NECC). Most EERIE models show this pattern as a well-defined thin filament, contrary to the pattern in EN4 which is weaker and smoother. Although we are considering control climate simulations, the SSS pattern in the EERIE models is closer to the recent CCI dataset (figure AM4b), and may be realistic. In IFS-FESOM and IFS-NEMO, the river runoffs are not fully coupled, but rather prescribed as climatological. It is thus very surprising to find that the salinity is so different in these two models especially along the coast of

Africa; the differences are probably related to very different precipitation over the ocean in this region (figure 22).

Figure 24 : Climatological SSS (in PSU) in the month of August in the tropical Atlantic, for observation datasets (EN4 and ESA CCI) and EERIE models.

In the Indian Ocean, the Bay of Bengal is characterized by salinity lower than 31 PSU, due to the intense precipitation and continental river runoff (e.g., Chaitanya et al, 2015). Figure 25 represents the SSS in October, when it is low in the Bay of Bengal after the summer monsoon. The salinities vary across the EERIE models. Considering the North East Bengal (NEB) region (86°E to 96°E, 14°N to 23°N) the annual mean salinity is about 31.5 (Chaitanya et al., 2015). The CCI observations are lower (31.4) and EN4 a bit saltier (31.7), perhaps reflecting the different time periods of these datasets, or the fact that EN4 does not represent well the low salinities near the coast. The annual mean salinity in the NEB region is 26.8, 30.8, 32.3 and 32.6 for the models ICON, HadGEM3-CG5-EERIE, IFS-FESOM and IFS-NEMO, respectively. Clearly the river runoffs play a part: both the models coupled with IFS, with climatological runoffs, underestimate the spreading of the low salinity waters. The lowest salinity in ICON is certainly related to the positive bias in precipitation (Figure 22).

Figure 25 : Climatological SSS in the month of October in the Northern Indian Ocean, for observation datasets (EN4 and ESA CCI) and EERIE models. Note that there are missing data points in the CCI observations at some locations.

3.4.4 Summary

In conclusion, EERIE models have relatively low SSS biases at the global scale compared with CMIP6, except in the Arctic. This is likely related to improvements in the atmospheric models (reduced biases in evaporation and precipitation) although advection by the mean and eddy currents could play a key role in some eddy-rich regions, such as the Antarctic Circumpolar current. The high resolution of the EERIE models makes it possible to investigate the low salinity waters in coastal regions and their spreading into the interior of the ocean basins. However we need to better understand the sources of these low salinity coastal waters in the different models (prescribed vs. coupled runoffs, for example) in order to interpret the large inter-model differences.

3.5 Sea Ice

Sea ice is a sensitive climate indicator, strongly interacting with the ocean (Martinson 1990, Goosse and Fichefet, 1999, Docquier and Koenig, 2021) and the atmosphere (Budikova 2009, Raphael et al., 2011). Arctic and Antarctic sea ice also form a base for polar marine ecosystems (Arrigo & Thomas, 2004, Lannuzel et al., 2020). With its large coverage and high albedo, sea ice impacts global radiative balance as well as modulates the warming of the polar oceans (Hall, 2004). These features also make sea ice a key agent in a spectrum of feedbacks in the polar regions (Goosse et al., 2018). Due to its key role in the transformation of Antarctic surface water to Dense shelf water (precursor or Antarctic Bottom Water) and Antarctic Intermediate Water, sea ice also impacts the amount of anthropogenic heat and carbon absorbed into the Southern Ocean, highlighting the relevance of understanding the processes that drive sea ice changes in our earth system (Abernathey et al., 2016, Frölicher et al., 2015).

Mesoscale processes that impact sea ice growth and melt rates cannot be resolved in the non-eddy coarse resolution climate models. This is especially challenging as the Rossby radius is much smaller at the higher latitudes. Mesoscale eddies impact sea ice dynamically: converging or diverging sea ice at the eddy core; and thermodynamically forming or melting sea ice due to changes in the eddy core temperature (PV Huot et al., 2022, Gupta et al., 2020, Manucharyan & Thompson, 2017). Observational studies combined with regional model studies have shown evidence for rich eddy activity in the polar oceans under sea ice (Manucharyan & Thompson, 2017, Auger et al., 2023). These studies also demonstrate that thermodynamic and mechanical coupling between the eddies and sea ice affect not only the sea ice mass, but also the heat and freshwater fluxes, and mixed layer depth in the ocean, as well as the wind speed, cloud cover and precipitation in the atmosphere (Manucharyan & Thompson, 2017, PV Huot et al., 2022).

Here we compare the simulated sea ice from eddy-rich EERIE models with the satellite observations of sea ice concentration: OSI SAF (OSI-450-a; EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility, 2015); and sea ice thickness: GIOMAS (Global Ice-Ocean Modeling and Assimilation System; Zhang & Rothrock, 2003). We used the monthly averaged fractional sea ice cover from OSI SAF that is provided at 25 km horizontal resolution to produce climatology for the period 1980 to 2000. GIOMAS is not strictly observational data, it is assimilated from observed sea ice concentration, it has 0.8 degree (~60 km) horizontal resolution on average. We use the monthly outputs for 1980 to 2000 period from GIOMAS. Given the sea ice's sensitivity to climate, it should again be noted that the model simulations are 1850 or 1950-based, and hence one would expect the models to have more sea ice than the observation in the period used.

Figure 26: 1980-2000 mean summer and winter sea ice concentration for Arctic and Antarctic regions from OSI SAF. The red line represents the ice edge defined as 15% sea ice concentration.

3.5.1 Arctic Ocean

The annual expansion and contraction of sea ice produces arguably the largest physical variation on the planet (Handcock and Raphael, 2020). The annual sea ice area ranges from ~6 (~2) million km² in summer to ~15 (~16) million km² in winter for the Arctic and the Antarctic regions (Figure 26 and Figure 29 c and d). Simulated sea ice concentrations for the EERIE models for Arctic ocean (Figure 27) shows that out of the four models, HadGEM3 simulates summer and winter sea ice cover (Figure 27 second column) as well as the total sea ice area (Figure 29 b pink line) that are closest to the observation. Both IFS-FESOM and IFS-NEMO tend to overestimate the summer and winter Arctic sea ice cover (Figure 27 columns 3 and 4). The overestimation of sea ice cover is stronger in IFS-NEMO producing almost 2 million km² more sea ice area throughout the year than the observation (Figure 29 b orange line). In both IFS-NEMO and IFS-FESOM Arctic sea ice extends further south in the Atlantic sector, in the Barents Sea and Nordic Sea regions. The ICON model on the other hand simulates much lower Arctic winter and summer sea ice cover (Figure 27 first column). The ICON model has about 2 million km² of lower sea ice area in winter and has a more precipitous melt in summer (Figure 29 b maroon line).

The annual evolution of sea ice volume for the EERIE models (Figure 29f) shows a large bias for IFS-NEMO producing about $85 \cdot 10^3 \text{ km}^3$ sea ice volume, about four times that of GIOMAS. IFS-FESOM also overestimates sea ice volume, but only by 50% compared to IFS-NEMO. As in the case of sea ice extent, HadGEM3 estimates sea ice volume closer to the observation (here GIOMAS reanalysis). Also, ICON retains low sea ice volume throughout the year. Note that the problem in IFS-NEMO has been identified and is being corrected, see EERIE deliverable D4.1 (Roberts et al., 2024).

Figure 27: Summer and winter mean Arctic sea ice concentration in the EERIE models from 20 years of simulated data. Top row shows sea ice concentration in February and bottom row shows sea ice concentration in September. The cyan line shows the position of the ice edge (where the sea ice concentration is 15%) for the respective model and the red line shows the ice edge from observations (averaged over 20 years).

3.5.2 Southern Ocean

For the Southern Hemisphere, EERIE models do not manage to capture winter and summer sea ice distribution with good fidelity simultaneously. For example, amongst all the EERIE models HadGEM3 simulates summer sea ice closer to the observation, however, the winter sea ice cover is considerably lower in the Pacific Ocean sector (Figure 28 second column and pink line in 29 a).

Figure 28: Same as 26, for the Antarctic region.

Similarly, IFS-FESOM produces good representation of winter sea ice conditions, but it melts almost all sea ice in summer (Figure 28 third column and red line in Figure 29 a). As in the case with Arctic sea ice, IFS-NEMO overestimates Antarctic sea ice cover both in summer and winter. IFS-NEMO has about 2.5 and 5 million km² more sea ice area in summer and winter respectively (Orange line in Figure 29 a). While all other models have no or very low sea ice cover in summer, IFS-NEMO sustains a large area of sea ice cover in summer. Once again as with the case in the Arctic, among all EERIE models, ICON produces the lowest Antarctic sea ice cover in summer and winter. Interestingly, the winter sea ice extent in HadGEM3 and ICON have a similar loss of sea ice in the Pacific sector. ICON also loses sea ice cover in the northern flanks of King Haakon Sea and East Antarctic sector in the Indian sector.

For sea ice volume in the Antarctic, HadGEM3 simulates the annual evolution closer to that in GIOMAS. Similar to sea ice area, IFS-NEMO overestimates sea ice volume by approximately $5 \cdot 10^3$ km³ in summer and winter. ICON has a low sea ice volume bias throughout the year, and interestingly, IFS-FESOM also produces lower sea ice volume with a large bias in winter, indicating very low sea ice thickness simulated by the model.

Figure 29: Annual evolution of sea ice area in the Arctic and Antarctic regions. (a) and (b) Figure 1 from Roach et al (2020) showing the 1979–2014 mean seasonal cycle in SIA for the CMIP6 r1-ensemble (faint green lines), the CMIP6 multi-model mean (thick green dashed line), and three observational products (black lines) in (a) the Antarctic and (b) the Arctic. (c) and (d) show the 20 year mean seasonal cycle of Antarctic and Arctic sea ice area from the EERIE models compared against the observed OSI SAF sea ice area. (e) and (f) show the 20 year mean seasonal cycle of Antarctic and Arctic sea ice volume from the EERIE models compared against the reanalysis product GIOMAS.

3.5.3 Summary

CMIP6 models simulate consistently low summer Antarctic sea ice area (Roach et al., 2020) and have a large spread for winter. For EERIE models in comparison with CMIP6 ensemble mean, IFS-NEMO overestimates Antarctic sea ice area throughout the year and ICON has a low bias, yet it is not at the extreme low end of the CMIP6 spectrum. IFS-FESOM and HadGEM3 fall within reasonable range compared to CMIP6. In contrast to Antarctica, for the Arctic sea ice area, all EERIE models have less spread from the observations, except the low bias in ICON. ICON has low winter sea ice cover and delayed onset of sea ice freezing. As in the case of CMIP models, the intermodal standard deviation (with respect to observations) is larger for Antarctic sea ice area than Arctic sea ice area. In the case of sea ice volume, the high estimate of IFS-NEMO, especially in the Arctic, presents a large bias (Roberts et al., 2024). Beyond that ICON consistently simulates low sea ice volume and HadGEM3 simulates sea ice volume close to GIOMAS in both poles. However, it is to be noted that compared to CMIP models that are fine-tuned and spun up for a long period, EERIE models do manage to simulate good representation of sea ice with similar range to that of the CMIP6 ensemble.

3.6 Mixed-Layer Depth

The ocean mixed-layer is a layer at the surface of the ocean where ocean properties are vertically homogenized over the thickness of the layer. The mixed layer is a key feature of the climate system as it is at the interface between the ocean interior and the atmosphere or sea ice and plays an important role for air-sea interactions, climate feedbacks and marine ecosystems by controlling the exchanges of heat, carbon, nutrients or oxygen between the surface and the ocean interior. The deepest mixed-layers generally occur in winter and early spring when buoyancy loss through atmospheric cooling and increased wind speeds favor deep mixing. To the contrary, the shallowest mixed-layers occur in late summer, when atmospheric heating and reduced winds favor the restratification of the water column. A fair representation of the mixed-layer depth (MLD) in climate models is therefore of paramount importance for the ability to model the Earth's present and future climate conditions.

Modeled versus observed MLD have been compared during the different phases of the Coupled-Model Intercomparison project (CMIP) and have revealed systematic biases. MLDs are underestimated globally in Summer in most of the CMIP5 models (Huang et al., 2014) and in the Southern Ocean in winter (Sallée et al., 2013). Although improved compared to CMIP5, CMIP6 MLD

are overestimated at the location of deep-water formation in the subpolar Atlantic Ocean and in the Southern Ocean (Heuzé et al., 2021).

Figure 30: Figure 9.5 of the AR6 WG1 IPCC report (Fox-Kemper et al., 2021). The (a–b) winter row shows December–January–February (DJF) in the Northern Hemisphere and June–July–August (JJA) in the Southern Hemisphere; The (e–f) summer row shows JJA in the Northern Hemisphere and DJF in the Southern Hemisphere.

The multi-model mean MLD biases from the latest IPCC report (Fox-Kemper et al., 2021) is shown in Figure 30. It shows that MLDs in CMIP6 models are too deep in winter in the subpolar North Atlantic where the deep convection is supposed to occur (Greenland and Labrador seas), as well as in the Gulf stream and Kuroshio extension, in the Southern Ocean and in the Northern Mediterranean Sea. And that MLDs in Summer are too shallow almost everywhere, in particular in the sub equatorial regions of the Atlantic and Pacific oceans, where it is off by nearly 50m. More recently, Tréguier et al. (2023) have investigated the MLD representation in an ensemble of high-resolution models forced with the same atmospheric reanalysis. They show that the winter biases in the deep-water formation region are reduced in high-resolution models but not uniformly across models.

Here we investigate the MLD representation in the four EERIE models for the last 20 years of the control simulations. Note that for the AWI model, only 15 years (1975-1999) are used. We compare

the MLD of the models to a monthly climatology (de Boyer Montégut, 2022) at a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial resolution. The climatology is based on about 7.3 million profiles of temperature and salinity measurements made at sea between January 1970 and December 2021 and provided mostly by the ARGO program and the World Ocean Database. As in Fox-Kemper et al. (2021), we define the mixed-layer depth to be the depth where the potential density is 0.03 kg m^{-3} denser than at 10m. Moreover, we define the winter MLD as the mean of January, February and March in the Northern Hemisphere and the mean of July, August and September in the Southern Hemisphere, and reversely for the Summer.

3.6.1 Seasonal Mixed-Layer Depth

Figure 31: MLD from observations (de Boyer Montégut, 2022) in (a) winter and (b) summer.

The EERIE models represent the key spatial features of the observed MLD, with a MLD deeper than 300m in Winter in the Subpolar Atlantic and in the Southern Ocean (Figure 31a, 32a,c,e,g). Although some models (AWI and Met Office) exhibit a large pattern of deep convection in the Weddell sea that is not observed (Figure 32c,e). In addition, unlike the observations, the MPI model represents a winter deep MLD that extends into the polar Arctic Ocean (Figure 32a). In Summer, all models exhibit an increased MLD in the Subequatorial and Southern Ocean (Figure 32b,d,f,h), as observed (Figure 31b).

Figure 32: MLD from EERIE models: (a,b) ICON (MPI model); (c,d) IFS-FESOM (AWI model); (e,f) HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE-HH (Met Office model), (g,h) IFS-NEMO (BSC model). Left column is for Winter and Right column is for Summer.

3.6.2 Seasonal Biases

The positive winter bias of MLD in CMIP6 models (Figure 30) is overall reduced in EERIE models (Figure 33, 35a) especially in the Greenland Sea and in the Gulf Stream and Kuroshio extension. A positive bias persists in the Labrador Sea and in the Mediterranean Sea in most EERIE models but are substantially smaller in the MPI model (Figure 33a). In addition some of the EERIE models (AWI and Met Office) have a very deep winter mixed layer in the Weddell Sea (Figure 33b,c), which has an imprint on the multi-model mean bias (Figure 35). That bias was not observed in the multi-model mean of the CMIP6 models - for the Met Office model, this bias is associated with a sea ice polynya that occurs almost constantly (see Roberts et al. 2024). Overall, AWI and the Met Office models have the strongest winter biases, with Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 146m and 235m respectively (Table 6).

Figure 33: MLD winter bias relative to de Boyer Montégut (2022).

Table 6: MLD global average root mean square error (RMSE) relative to de Boyer (2022).

	MPI (ICON-O)	AWI (FESOM)	Met Office (NEMO)	BSC (NEMO)
Winter	54 m	146 m	235 m	63 m
Summer	8 m	12 m	7 m	7 m

The MLD summer biases has been overall reduced in EERIE models compared to CMIP6 models, although it is persistently negative in the subequatorial and subtropical regions (Figure 34, 35b). The models are comparable in terms of RMSE (Table 6). However, as already reported in Tréguier et al. (2023), models do not agree on the sign of the bias in the Southern Ocean. Here MPI and AWI models represent a MLD that is too shallow in the Southern Ocean in Summer (Figure 34a,b), while the MLD in the Met Office model is on average too deep (Figure 34c) and the MLD in the BSC model is too shallow South of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) and too deep north of the ACC (Figure 34d).

Figure 34: MLD summer bias relative to de Boyer Montégut (2023).

3.6.3 Summary

In conclusion, EERIE models have reasonable biases with respect to the observations, most of the existing biases in CMIP6 models are reduced in the EERIE models. However, the modeled MLD should be treated with care in some specific locations in Winter where large biases remain: the Southern Ocean for AWI and Met Office models and the Mediterranean Sea in AWI model.

Figure 35: MLD multi-model bias in (a) winter and (b) summer. Regions where the models have biases of different signs are hatched.

3.7 Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation

The North Atlantic, via the ocean circulation, is a key region in terms of heat transport to high latitudes (Johns et al., 2023; Trenberth & Fasullo, 2017) and carbon uptake from the atmosphere (Brown et al., 2021). The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) streamfunction (Figure 36) is a measure of the northward ocean volume transport, integrated zonally over the Atlantic basin and cumulatively from the top to the bottom of the ocean, as described in the formula:

$$\Psi(z) = \int_{x_0}^{x_1} \int_0^z v(x, z) dx dz,$$

where v represents the meridional velocity, x_0 and x_1 represent the western and eastern limits of the Atlantic basin, and z represents depth.

The AMOC, through its mean state and variability, affects climate in several ways, e.g. modulating regional temperatures in the Northern Hemisphere (Buckley & Marshall, 2016). Climate projections indicate a consistent AMOC weakening at increased CO₂ levels (Jackson et al., 2020), with important

effects on climate (Bellomo & Mehling, 2024). Also, as a potential climate tipping point (Lenton et al., 2008), the AMOC and its mechanisms need to be appropriately simulated to trustfully evaluate future climate change impacts.

Figure 36: Mean AMOC climatology averaged over an ensemble of 39 CMIP6 models at standard resolution (period 1980-2014). Extracted from Frigola et al. (in prep).

Here we describe the AMOC in the EERIE models that resolve ocean processes in the mesoscale, with nominal ocean resolutions of 10 km. An additional EERIE model (GC5-MM) with a coarser ocean grid (25 km) is also included in the analyses to help assess the role of resolution. For all models, data from the last 20 years of their respective control runs are employed: years 2031-2050 for HadGEM3-GC5-EERIE, 1991-2010 for ICON, and 1950-1969 for IFS-FESOM. We also consider a multi-model mean of 39 CMIP6 historical simulations from non-eddy-resolving models as a reference (Figure 36).

Figure 37: AMOC in depth space averaged over 20 years of control for the EERIE models.

3.7.1 AMOC mean state and variability

Figure 37 shows the AMOC mean state in EERIE models. GC5-HH and IFS-FESOM exhibit stronger AMOC upper cells compared to GC5-MM, ICON, and the CMIP6 multi-model mean. The CMIP6 multi-model mean also shows a deeper AMOC cell in the Northern Hemisphere than the three EERIE models. A weaker AMOC in GC5-MM compared to GC5-HH suggests an increased AMOC strength at higher resolution as in Roberts et al. (2020). Nevertheless, the role of resolution in AMOC strength is still a matter of debate (Sein et al., 2018) as the AMOC and its strength are largely model dependent. GC5 models present a stronger Antarctic Bottom Water cell compared to the other two models and the CMIP6 ensemble mean (Figure 36). It is worth noting that the AMOC calculation in ICON is slightly different from the other models, binning first the vertical velocities in 1° latitude bins, summing them along the longitude dimension before applying a smoothing filter (3° running mean). This makes the AMOC streamfunction quite smooth in ICON compared to the other models, as observed in Figure 37.

Figure 38: As in Figure 2 but showing standard deviation from monthly data.

The standard deviation of the AMOC from monthly and yearly data is shown in Figures 38 and 39, respectively. AMOC variability is strong at subannual time scales where it is mainly driven by local wind forcing, meanwhile at interannual timescales its variability is weaker and associated with the geostrophic component of the AMOC (Figures 38 and 39; Buckley & Marshall, 2016). At monthly time scales, ICON presents larger variability near the tropics compared to the other models (Figure 38), which suggests a much stronger influence of the Trade winds. At interannual time scales, GC5-HH and IFS-FESOM show the largest variability (Figure 39). This is particularly interesting when comparing GC5-HH to GC5-MM, as resolving the eddies seems to largely enhance the interannual variability.

Figure 39: As in Figure 38 but from yearly data

3.7.2 Comparison with observations

We now perform a comparison with AMOC observational data. Continuous measurements of the AMOC started in 2004 within the RAPID programme at 26.5°N and span to present-day. RAPID data are mainly based on observations of density profiles from a mooring array crossing the Atlantic from west to east at 26.5°N, combined with additional direct transport measurements, and reanalysed winds for Ekman transport estimates (Johns et al., 2023). In Figure 40a the modelled AMOC is compared with observations at the RAPID array. Our results suggest that GC5-MM and ICON are the models that better capture the AMOC maximum at around 1000 m compared to the stronger GC5-HH and IFS-FESOM values. AMOC in the CMIP6 ensemble appears also too strong compared to RAPID (Table 7). We note, however, that at deep levels, AMOC transports calculated from model velocities might differ significantly from those obtained with the RAPID method so that direct comparison might not be appropriate below ~3000 m (Danabasoglu et al., 2021; Roberts et al., 2013).

Figure 40: (a) Meridional volume transport at 26.5°N averaged over 20 years of control. The black solid line shows RAPID observations for the period April 2004-February 2023. RAPID data can be downloaded directly from the site <https://rapid.ac.uk/>. The black dashed line shows the mean AMOC from an ensemble of 39 CMIP6 models at eddy-parameterized/-permitting resolutions (extracted from Frigola et al., in prep.). (b) As in (a) but for the standard deviation from model monthly data. The black dashed (solid) line shows RAPID observations at subdaily (monthly) resolution. (c) As in (a) but for 34.5°S. The black solid line shows SAMBA observations for the period September 2013-July 2017 (from Kersalé et al., 2020, pers. comm.). Note: for GC5-HH, latitude 34.15°S was used.

The simulated monthly AMOC variability at 26.5°N shows general good agreement with observations (Figure 40b), although most models tend to overestimate it at the surface. For ICON, variability above 2000 m is slightly weaker than for the other models. This is also visible in Figure 38 from 20°N northwards. Standard deviation of RAPID data at their original sub-daily temporal resolution (black dashed line) indicates significant variability at submonthly time scales, which was not available from the models.

Further recent efforts have been put into extending AMOC monitoring in the South Atlantic. Observations from nine pressure-equipped inverted echo sounder moorings in the SAMOC Basin-wide Array (SAMBA; Kersalé et al., 2020) allow us to validate the simulated AMOC at 34.5°S (Figure 40c). The ICON and IFS-FESOM models seem to capture better the maximum AMOC strength at that latitude (Table 7). By contrast, the AMOC abyssal cell appears to be better represented in the two GC5 models, although located at a shallower depth compared to SAMBA data (Figure 40c).

Table 7: Maximum AMOC at 26.5°N and 34.5°S from models and observations. Units in Sv.

models / observations	max. at 26.5°N	max. at 34.5°S
GC5-MM	16.13	14.79
GC5-HH	19.32	18.95
ICON	17.91	17.46
IFS-FESOM	19.92	17.41
CMIP6	18.79	–
RAPID	16.60	–
SAMBA	–	17.72

3.7.3 Summary

GC5-HH and IFS-FESOM show the strongest AMOC cells, followed by the CMIP6 ensemble mean. Also the interannual variability is stronger in these two EERIE models. By contrast, ICON and GC5-MM show better agreement with the climatology of RAPID observations compared to the other models and CMIP6, which tend to overestimate it. Likewise, EERIE models capture reasonably well the AMOC monthly variability shown in RAPID observations. The AMOC abyssal cell, as characterized by the observation-based SAMBA array, is better represented in the GC5 models compared to CMIP6, ICON and IFS-FESOM. Regarding the impact of horizontal resolution, a comparison of GC5-HH with its lower resolution counterpart suggests an AMOC strengthening and larger interannual variability at increased resolution, although this conclusion might be model-dependent and should then be further tested in the remaining EERIE models.

3.8 Climate variability : El Niño Southern Oscillation

El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) is a critical climate phenomenon characterized by variations in sea surface temperature (SST) across the equatorial Pacific Ocean. These variations significantly influence global climate patterns, leading to year-to-year climate variability that affects ecosystems, weather patterns, and human activities worldwide. ENSO consists of two main phases: El Niño, which is associated with warmer SSTs, and La Niña, which corresponds to cooler SSTs. The impacts of ENSO are profound, influencing atmospheric circulation, precipitation patterns, and even global

temperatures (Trenberth, 1997). Here we compare the ENSO variability in the EERIE model to the observed one using the HadISST product (Rayner et al., 2003), providing an optimal interpolation of the SST at a 1° and monthly resolution, from 1870 to date. It should be noted that ENSO has variability on interannual to multi-decadal timescales, and hence caution is needed in assessing models over just several decades as shown here.

3.8.1 ENSO Index: Models and Observation

In our analysis of ENSO variability among the EERIE models, we observe that most models effectively replicate the observed ENSO variability in the equatorial Pacific Ocean (Figure 41). However, the ICON model exhibits limitations in capturing this variability; specifically, the SST fluctuations in the ENSO region are weaker than expected (Figure 41c). In contrast, both the IFS-FESOM and IFS-NEMO models demonstrate amplitude variations that closely align with reanalysis data (Figures 41b,d). The reasons behind ICON's discrepancies in simulating ENSO variability are currently under investigation.

Figure 41: Niño 3.4 index in the (a) HadISST (1950-1969) and in the control simulation with 1950 radiative forcing from (b) IFS-FESOM (20 years) in (c) ICON (20 years), in (d) IFS-NEMO (last 20 years of coupled-spin up) and in the last 20 years of control simulation with 1850 radiative forcing from (e) HadGEM3-GC5-HH (f) HadGEM3-GC5-MM.

3.8.2 ENSO Spatial Patterns

When examining the spatial patterns associated with ENSO time series shown in Figure 41, we find a notable resemblance between observed patterns and those generated by the models (Figure 42). The IFS-FESOM model closely mirrors observed patterns, with a significant exception being the

emergence of a cold tongue in the tropical Atlantic and along the Benguela coast that is not present in HadISST data. For the ICON model, the SST patterns over mid to high-latitude oceans show limited similarity to observed patterns. Meanwhile, IFS-NEMO also aligns well with the pattern from HadISST, particularly over the South Pacific Ocean; however, it fails to capture cold SST anomalies in the western North Pacific. Similar to IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO exhibits a tendency to simulate cold tongue SST anomalies over the tropical Atlantic in association with ENSO events. Both the high and medium resolution version of HadGEM3-GC5 model closely resembles the observed SST anomaly pattern, except over the Indian Ocean. The pattern over the north Pacific Ocean gets closer to the observations in the high resolution compared to the low resolution.

Figure 42: The spatial regression of the SST on the Niño 3.4 index shown in Figure 41 depicting the ENSO pattern in (a) HadISST, (b) IFS-FESOM, (c) ICON, (d) IFS-NEMO, (e) HadGEM3-GC5-HH, (f) HadGEM3-GC5-MM.

3.8.3 Summary

Our analysis of ENSO variability among the EERIE models reveals that most models effectively capture the observed ENSO variability in the equatorial Pacific Ocean, with IFS-FESOM, IFS-NEMO and HadGEM3-GC5 showing amplitude variations that align closely with the observations. In contrast, the ICON model struggles to replicate this variability, exhibiting weaker SST fluctuations in the ENSO region. The spatial patterns associated with ENSO time series show significant similarities between model simulations and observed data. Notably, IFS-FESOM closely resembles observed patterns, although it introduces a cold tongue in the tropical Atlantic that is absent in HadISST. ICON displays limited resemblance in mid to high-latitude SST patterns, while IFS-NEMO aligns well with observations over the South Pacific but fails to capture cold anomalies in the western North Pacific. Both IFS-FESOM and IFS-NEMO exhibit tendencies to simulate cold tongue SST anomalies over the

tropical Atlantic in relation to ENSO events, which diverge from observed patterns. Whereas the associated SST pattern over the north Pacific Ocean gets closer to the observations in the HadGEM3-GC5-HH compared to HADGEM3-GC5-MM.

The ability of climate models to accurately simulate ENSO is crucial for understanding future climate scenarios. Improved representation of ENSO characteristics can enhance predictive capabilities regarding climate variability and its impacts on global weather patterns. Recent studies indicate that advancements in model physics and resolution are vital for addressing current biases (Eyring et al., 2016). Further research would focus on examining the implications of improved ENSO simulations on long-term climate.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

The major improvements in this set of eddy-rich coupled climate models compared to previous lower resolution climate models stand out in the ocean dynamics itself. The EERIE climate models indeed demonstrate significant reductions in SSH biases compared to CMIP5 and CMIP6, particularly in the tropical Pacific and northwestern Indian Ocean, and offer better representation of major currents like the Kuroshio Current and eddy variability all around the globe. Some of the EERIE models are even capable of resolving fine-scale boundary currents such as the East Greenland Coastal Current, which is a real success, unprecedented in climate modelling efforts.

However, some models can suffer from persistent biases that are yet not well understood and call for deeper investigations. For example some of the largest biases in the sea-surface velocity are around the Western boundary of the Equatorial Pacific in all models and the Gulf Stream eddy variability also exhibits persistent issues in its location.

When it comes to model validation at depth, the spatio-temporal resolution of observations can become a limitation. For example, gridded velocity products in the deep ocean should be used with care when evaluating model biases, which are on the same order of magnitude as the differences seen between two observational products. Better products or alternative bias evaluation methods are required. Some specific dataset however can be used to validate the models at specific locations. Here comparing the meridional volume transport at 26.5°N in the North Atlantic (AMOC) to the observations of the RAPID array shows that EERIE models (ICON and HadGEM3-GC5-MM in particular) are in a better agreement with the observations than the CMIP6 models, which tend to overestimate it, and capture reasonably well the AMOC monthly variability shown in RAPID observations.

Despite an improvement of the ocean dynamics, no major and systematic bias improvement have been noticed in SST, SSS or Sea Ice. For example, SST biases are uneven across models, with some models having drastically reduced biases compared to the CMIP models, and others having larger

biases. In addition, SST biases are sometimes correlated with biases in other variables (sea ice, evaporation-precipitations, SSS, etc.); all these biases are therefore not independent. Likewise, SSS is strongly influenced by the precipitation which varies a lot across the EERIE models (and across CMIP6 coupled models in general). Regarding sea ice, EERIE models simulate a sea ice extent within the range of the CMIP6 model ensemble. Of which ICON and IFS-NEMO are on the lowest and highest range of the spectrum for EERIE models in terms of sea ice production, and HadGEM3-GC5 being the closest to the observations. The cold bias in IFS-NEMO and IFS-FESOM, especially in the Arctic, can explain the overestimation of the winter Arctic sea ice extent, largely into the Barents Sea region in the Atlantic sector in these models. Likewise, the warm bias in ICON at both poles can explain why this model fails to capture the sea ice extent in the Pacific sector, especially in the Amundsen and Bellingshausen Sea regions.

However, the transport of heat and salt by mesoscale eddies is likely an important factor in specific regions, like the tropical Atlantic or the Southern Ocean. This report intended to give a global overview of the EERIE models evaluation and more in depth regional studies are necessary to explore the mechanisms and appreciate the improvements brought by eddy-rich models. Furthermore, only the surface temperature and salinity have been considered in the present report, but eddy transports occur over the whole water column. It will be interesting to investigate the depth-integrated contribution of eddies to meridional transports of heat and salt (following for example Treguier et al 2014). Finally, eddy-rich coupled models suggest that the eddy activity will change in the future, understanding how these changes will affect the redistribution of heat and salt in the world ocean is also a promising research path.

Finally, this set of simulations represent the Phase 1 of EERIE model developments. This report will likely feed in the reflection and discussions to improve the simulation configurations in Phase 2.

5 References

Abernathy, R. P., Cerovecki, I., Holland, P. R., Newsom, E., Mazloff, M., & Talley, L. D. (2016). Water-mass transformation by sea ice in the upper branch of the Southern Ocean overturning. *Nature Geoscience*, 9(8), 596-601.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2749>

Arrigo, K. R., & Thomas, D. N. (2004). Large scale importance of sea ice biology in the Southern Ocean. *Antarctic Science*, 16(4), 471-486.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0954102004002263>

Auger, Matthis, Jean-Baptiste Sallée, Andrew F. Thompson, Etienne Pauthenet, and Pierre Prandi. "Southern Ocean Ice-Covered Eddy Properties From Satellite Altimetry." *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 128, no. 4 (2023): e2022JC019363.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2022JC019363>

Axell, L. B. (2002). Wind-driven internal waves and Langmuir circulations in a numerical ocean model of the southern Baltic Sea. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 107(C11), 25–1.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2001JC000922>

Barnier, B., Madec, G., Penduff, T., Molines, J. M., Treguier, A. M., Le Sommer, J., Beckmann, A., Biastoch, A., Boning, C., Dengg, J., Derval, C., Durand, E., Gulev, S., Remy, E., Talandier, C., Theetten, S., Maltrud, M., McClean, J., & De Cuevas, B. (2006). Impact of partial steps and momentum advection schemes in a global ocean circulation model at eddy-permitting resolution. *Ocean Dynamics*, 56(5–6), 543–567.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10236-006-0082-1>

Bellomo, K., & Mehling, O. (2024). Impacts and State-Dependence of AMOC Weakening in a Warming Climate. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 51(10), e2023GL107624.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2023GL107624>

Blockley, E., Fiedler, E., Ridley, J., Roberts, L., West, A., Copsey, D., Feltham, D., Graham, T., Livings, D., Rousset, C., Schroeder, D., & Vancoppenolle, M. (2024). The sea ice component of GC5: Coupling SI3 to HadGEM3 using conductive fluxes. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 17(17), 6799–6817.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-17-6799-2024>

Bonjean, F., & Lagerloef, G. S. E. (2002). Diagnostic Model and Analysis of the Surface Currents in the Tropical Pacific Ocean. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 32(10), 2938–2954.

[https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(2002\)032%3C2938:DMAAOT%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(2002)032%3C2938:DMAAOT%3E2.0.CO;2)

Boutin, J.; Vergely, J.-L.; Reul, N.; Catany, R.; Jouanno, J.; Martin, A.; Rouffi, F.; Bertino, L.; Bonjean, F.; Corato, G.; Gévaudan, M.; Guimbard, S.; Khvorostyanov, D.; Kolodziejczyk, N.; Matthews, M.; Olivier, L.;

Raj, R.; Rémy, E.; Reverdin, G.; Supply, A.; Thouvenin-Masson, C.; Vialard, J.; Sabia, R.; Mecklenburg, S. (2024): ESA Sea Surface Salinity Climate Change Initiative (Sea_Surface_Salinity_cci): Monthly sea surface salinity product on a global grid, v04.41, for 2010 to 2022. NERC EDS Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, date of citation.

<https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/7cc16c0d8d2f49278ed5ebf8341ed40b/>

de Boyer Montégut, C. (2022): Mixed layer depth climatology computed with a density threshold criterion of 0.03 kg/m³ from 10 m depth value, SEANOE [data set],

<https://doi.org/10.17882/91774>

Brown, P. J., McDonagh, E. L., Sanders, R., Watson, A. J., Wanninkhof, R., King, B. A., Smeed, D. A., Baringer, M. O., Meinen, C. S., Schuster, U., Yool, A., & Messias, M.-J. (2021). Circulation-driven variability of Atlantic anthropogenic carbon transports and uptake. *Nature Geoscience*, 14(8), 571–577.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-021-00774-5>

Buckley, M. W., & Marshall, J. (2016). Observations, inferences, and mechanisms of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation: A review. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 54(1), 5–63.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/2015RG000493>

Budikova, D. (2009). Role of Arctic sea ice in global atmospheric circulation: A review. *Global and Planetary Change*, 68(3), 149-163.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2009.04.001>

Caneill, R., F. Roquet, G. Madec, and J. Nycander, 2022: The Polar Transition from Alpha to Beta Regions Set by a Surface Buoyancy Flux Inversion. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 52, 1887–1902.

<https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-21-0295.1>

Chaitanya, A.V.S., Durand, F., Mathew, S. et al. Observed year-to-year sea surface salinity variability in the Bay of Bengal during the 2009–2014 period. *Ocean Dynamics* 65, 173–186 (2015).

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10236-014-0802-x>

Chassignet, E. P., & Marshall, D. P. (2008). Gulf Stream Separation in Numerical Ocean Models. In *Ocean Modeling in an Eddying Regime* (pp. 39–61). *American Geophysical Union (AGU)*.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/177GM05>

Chelton, D. B., Deszoeke, R. A., Schlax, M. G., El Naggar, K., & Siwertz, N. (1998). Geographical variability of the first baroclinic Rossby radius of deformation. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 28(3), 433–460.

[https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(1998\)028<0433:GVOTFB>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(1998)028<0433:GVOTFB>2.0.CO;2)

Cravatte, S., Kessler, W. S., & Marin, F. (2012). Intermediate zonal jets in the tropical Pacific Ocean observed by Argo floats. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 42(9), 1475-1485.

<https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-11-0206.1>

Danabasoglu, G., Castruccio, F. S., Small, R. J., Tomas, R., Frajka-Williams, E., & Lankhorst, M. (2021). Revisiting AMOC Transport Estimates From Observations and Models. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 48(10), e2021GL093045.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL093045>

Daniault, N., Mercier, H., & Lherminier, P. (2011). The 1992–2009 transport variability of the East Greenland-Irminger Current at 60°N. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 38(7).

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2011GL046863>

Danilov, S., Wang, Q., Timmermann, R., Iakovlev, N., Sidorenko, D., Kimmritz, M., Jung, T., & Schröter, J. (2015). Finite-Element Sea Ice Model (FESIM), version 2. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 8(6), 1747–1761.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-1747-2015>

Delpech, A., Cravatte, S., Marin, F., Morel, Y., Gronchi, E., & Kestenare, E. (2020). Observed tracer fields structuration by mid-depth zonal jets in the tropical Pacific. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 50(2), 281-304.

<https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-20-0180.1>

Delpech, A., Ménesguen, C., Morel, Y., Thomas, L. N., Marin, F., Cravatte, S., & Le Gentil, S. (2021). Intra-annual Rossby waves destabilization as a potential driver of low-latitude zonal jets: Barotropic dynamics. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 51(2), 365-384.

<https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-19-0132.1>

Delpech A. (2021). Dynamics at Low Latitudes in the Deep Ocean: Generation and Impacts of Zonal Jets. PhD Thesis, *University of Toulouse* (France).

Docquier, D., & Koenigk, T. (2021). A review of interactions between ocean heat transport and Arctic sea ice. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(12), 123002.

<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac30be>

Dohan, K. (2024, March). Ocean Surface Current Analyses Real-time (OSCAR) v2.0 User's Handbook. *Earth & Space Research*, 1107 NE 45th St., Suite 320, Seattle WA 98105-4656.

<https://www.esr.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/oscarv2.0guide.pdf>

Durack, P.J. et al. Ocean Salinities Reveal Strong Global Water Cycle Intensification During 1950 to 2000. *Science* 336, 455-458(2012). DOI:10.1126/science.1212222

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1212222>

Roberts, M. J., Jung, T., Ortega, P., Ghosh, R., Wachsmann, F., von Storch, J.-S., Kroeger, J., Aengenheyster, M., & Roberts, C. (2024). Phase 1 simulations, including HighResMIP and CMIP6-PI-control simulations.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14288726>

Embury, O., Merchant, C.J., Good, S.A., Rayner, N.A., Høyer, J.L., Atkinson, C., Block, T., Alerskans, E., Pearson, K.J., Worsfold, M., McCarroll, N., Donlon, C., (2024). Satellite-based time-series of sea-surface temperature since 1980 for climate applications. *Scientific Data* 11, 326. doi:

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03147-w>

ESR, Dohan, K. (2022). Ocean Surface Current Analyses Real-time (OSCAR) Surface Currents—Final 0.25 Degree (Version 2.0). (Version 2.0) [Dataset]. PO. DAAC.

<https://doi.org/10.5067/OSCAR-25F20>

Eyring, V., N.P. Gillett, K.M. Achuta Rao, R. Barimalala, M. Barreiro Parrillo, N. Bellouin, C. Cassou, P.J. Durack, Y. Kosaka, S. McGregor, S. Min, O. Morgenstern, and Y. Sun, 2021: Human Influence on the Climate System. In *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S.L. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M.I. Gomis, M. Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J.B.R. Matthews, T.K. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu, and B. Zhou (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 423–552, doi: 10.1017/9781009157896.005.

<https://doi:10.1017/9781009157896.005>

Ezer, T. (2016). Revisiting the problem of the Gulf Stream separation: On the representation of topography in ocean models with different types of vertical grids. *Ocean Modelling*, 104, 15–27.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2016.05.008>

Fox-Kemper, B., Hewitt, H. T., Xiao, C., Adalgeirsdottir, G., Drijfhout, S. S., Edwards, T. L., Golledge, N. R., Hemer, M., Kopp, R. E., Krinner, G., Mix, A., Notz, D., Nowicki, S., Nurhati, I. S., Ruiz, L., Sallee, J.-B., Slangen, A. B. A., and Yu, Y. *Climate Change 2021 (2021): The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, Cambridge University Press, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 1211–1362,

<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896.011>

Frölicher, T. L., Sarmiento, J. L., Paynter, D. J., Dunne, J. P., Krasting, J. P., & Winton, M. (2015). Dominance of the Southern Ocean in anthropogenic carbon and heat uptake in CMIP5 models. *Journal of Climate*, 28(2), 862-886.

<https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-14-00117.1>

Gill, A. E. (1974). The stability of planetary waves on an infinite beta-plane. *Geophysical and Astrophysical Fluid Dynamics*, 6(1), 29-47.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/03091927409365786>

Good, S. A., M. J. Martin and N. A. Rayner, 2013. EN4: quality-controlled ocean temperature and salinity profiles and monthly objective analyses with uncertainty estimates, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 118, 6704-6716, doi: 10.1002/2013JC009067

<https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JC009067>

Goosse, H., & Fichefet, T. (1999). Importance of ice-ocean interactions for the global ocean circulation: A model study. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 104(C10), 23337-23355.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/1999JC900215>

Goosse, H., Kay, J. E., Armour, K. C., Bodas-Salcedo, A., Chepfer, H., Docquier, D., ... & Vancoppenolle, M. (2018). Quantifying climate feedbacks in polar regions. *Nature communications*, 9(1), 1919.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-04173-0>

Guiavarc'h, C., Storkey, D., Blaker, A. T., Blockley, E., Megann, A., Hewitt, H. T., Bell, M. J., Calvert, D., Copsey, D., Sinha, B., Moreton, S., Mathiot, P., & An, B. (2024). GOSI9: UK Global Ocean and Sea Ice configurations. *EGUsphere*, 2024, 1–38.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-805>

Gupta, M., Marshall, J., Song, H., Campin, J. M., & Meneghello, G. (2020). Sea-ice melt driven by ice-ocean stresses on the mesoscale. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 125(11), e2020JC016404.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JC016404>

Gregory, J.M., Griffies, S.M., Hughes, C.W. et al. Concepts and Terminology for Sea Level: Mean, Variability and Change, Both Local and Global. *Surv Geophys* 40, 1251–1289 (2019).

<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/10/7/074008>

Hall, A. (2004). The role of surface albedo feedback in climate. *Journal of climate*, 17(7), 1550-1568.

[https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442\(2004\)017%3C1550:TROSAF%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(2004)017%3C1550:TROSAF%3E2.0.CO;2)

Heuzé, C. (2020). Antarctic bottom water and North Atlantic deep water in CMIP6 models. *Ocean Science Discussions*, 2020, 1-38.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/os-17-59-2021>

Hewitt, H. T., Roberts, M. J., Hyder, P., Graham, T., Rae, J., Belcher, S. E., ... & Wood, R. A. (2016). The impact of resolving the Rossby radius at mid-latitudes in the ocean: Results from a high-resolution version of the Met Office GC2 coupled model. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 9(10), 3655-3670.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-3655-2016>

Hewitt, H. T., Roberts, M., Mathiot, P., Biastoch, A., Blockley, E., Chassignet, E. P., Fox-Kemper, B., Hyder, P., Marshall, D. P., Popova, E., Treguier, A.-M., Zanna, L., Yool, A., Yu, Y., Beadling, R., Bell, M., Kuhlbrodt, T., Arsouze, T., Bellucci, A., ... Zhang, Q. (2020). Resolving and Parameterising the Ocean Mesoscale in Earth System Models. *Current Climate Change Reports*, 6(4), 137–152.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40641-020-00164-w>

Hohenegger, C., Korn, P., Linardakis, L., Redler, R., Schnur, R., Adamidis, P., Bao, J., Bastin, S., Behraves, M., Bergemann, M., Biercamp, J., Bockelmann, H., Brokopf, R., Brüggemann, N., Casaroli, L., Chegini, F., Datseris, G., Esch, M., George, G., ... Stevens, B. (2023). ICON-Sapphire: Simulating the components of the Earth system and their interactions at kilometer and subkilometer scales. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 16(2), 779–811.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-779-2023>

Huang, C. J., Qiao, F., & Dai, D. (2014). Evaluating CMIP5 simulations of mixed layer depth during summer. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 119(4), 2568-2582.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JC009535>

Huot, P. V., Kittel, C., Fichet, T., Jourdain, N. C., & Fettweis, X. (2022). Effects of ocean mesoscale eddies on atmosphere–sea ice–ocean interactions off Adélie Land, East Antarctica. *Climate Dynamics*, 59(1), 41-60.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-021-06115-x>

Hunke, E. C., & Dukowicz, J. K. (1997). An Elastic–Viscous–Plastic Model for Sea Ice Dynamics. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 27(9), 1849–1867.

[https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(1997\)027](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(1997)027)

Ichikawa, H., & Chaen, M. (2000). Seasonal variation of heat and freshwater transports by the Kuroshio in the East China Sea. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 24(1), 119–129.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-7963\(99\)00082-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-7963(99)00082-2)

Jackson, L. C., Roberts, M. J., Hewitt, H. T., Iovino, D., Koenig, T., Meccia, V. L., Roberts, C. D., Ruprich-Robert, Y., & Wood, R. A. (2020). Impact of ocean resolution and mean state on the rate of AMOC weakening. *Climate Dynamics*, 55(7), 1711–1732.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-020-05345-9>

Johns, W. E., Elipot, S., Smeed, D. A., Moat, B., King, B., Volkov, D. L., & Smith, R. H. (2023). Towards two decades of Atlantic Ocean mass and heat transports at 26.5° N. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 381(2262), 20220188.

<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2022.0188>

Jungclaus, J. H., Lorenz, S. J., Schmidt, H., Brovkin, V., Brüggemann, N., Chegini, F., Crüger, T., De-Vrese, P., Gayler, V., Giorgetta, M. A., Gutjahr, O., Haak, H., Hagemann, S., Hanke, M., Ilyina, T., Korn, P., Kröger, J., Linardakis, L., Mehlmann, C., ... Claussen, M. (2022). The ICON Earth System Model Version 1.0. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 14(4), e2021MS002813.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2021MS002813>

Katsumata, K., & Yoshinari, H. (2010). Uncertainties in global mapping of Argo drift data at the parking level. *Journal of Oceanography*, 66(4), 553–569.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10872-010-0046-4>

Katsumata, K. (2011). G-YoMaHa (Objective mapped velocity at 1000 dbar derived from trajectories of Argo floats) [Dataset]. JAMSTEC.

<https://doi.org/10.17596/0000103>

Kersalé, M., Meinen, C. S., Perez, R. C., Le Hénaff, M., Valla, D., Lamont, T., Sato, O. T., Dong, S., Terre, T., van Caspel, M., Chidichimo, M. P., van den Berg, M., Speich, S., Piola, A. R., Campos, E. J. D., Ansorge, I., Volkov, D. L., Lumpkin, R., & Garzoli, S. L. (2020). Highly variable upper and abyssal overturning cells in the South Atlantic. *Science Advances*, 6(32), eaba7573.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aba7573>

Korn, P. (2017). Formulation of an unstructured grid model for global ocean dynamics. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 339, 525–552.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2017.03.009>

Korn, P. (2018). A structure-preserving discretization of ocean parametrizations on unstructured grids. *Ocean Modelling*, 132, 73–90.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2018.10.002>

Korn, P., Brüggemann, N., Jungclaus, J. H., Lorenz, S. J., Gutjahr, O., Haak, H., Linardakis, L., Mehlmann, C., Mikolajewicz, U., Notz, D., Putrasahan, D. A., Singh, V., von Storch, J.-S., Zhu, X., & Marotzke, J. (2022). ICON-O: The Ocean Component of the ICON Earth System Model—Global Simulation Characteristics and Local Telescoping Capability. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 14(10), e2021MS002952.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2021MS002952>

Lannuzel, D., Tedesco, L., Van Leeuwe, M., Campbell, K., Flores, H., Delille, B., ... & Wongpan, P. (2020). The future of Arctic sea-ice biogeochemistry and ice-associated ecosystems. *Nature Climate Change*, 10(11), 983-992.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-00940-4>

Laurindo, L. C., Mariano, A. J., & Lumpkin, R. (2017). An improved near-surface velocity climatology for the global ocean from drifter observations. *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers*, 124, 73–92.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr.2017.04.009>

Laurindo, L., Mariano, A., & Lumpkin, R. (2023). Laurindo et al. V3.10 (Version 3.10) [Dataset].

https://www.aoml.noaa.gov/ftp/phod/pub/lumpkin/drifter_climatology/version_3.10/drifter_monthly_means.nc

Le Bras, I. A.-A., Straneo, F., Holte, J., & Holliday, N. P. (2018). Seasonality of Freshwater in the East Greenland Current System From 2014 to 2016. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 123(12),

8828–8848.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2018JC014511>

Lebedev, K. V., Yoshinari, H., Maximenko, N. A., & Hacker, P. W. (2007, June 12). YoMaHa'07: Velocity data assessed from trajectories of Argo floats at parking level and at the sea surface. *IPRC Technical Note No. 4(2)*.

<http://apdrc.soest.hawaii.edu/projects/yomaha/yomaha07/YoMaHa070612.pdf>

Lenton, T. M., Held, H., Kriegler, E., Hall, J. W., Lucht, W., Rahmstorf, S., & Schellnhuber, H. J. (2008). Tipping elements in the Earth's climate system. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 105(6), 1786–1793.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0705414105>

Liu, Y., Cheng, L., Pan, Y. et al. How Well Do CMIP6 and CMIP5 Models Simulate the Climatological Seasonal Variations in Ocean Salinity?. *Advances in Atmospheric Sciences*. 39, 1650–1672 (2022).

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00376-022-1381-2>

Lyu, K., X. Zhang, and J. A. Church, 2020: Regional Dynamic Sea Level Simulated in the CMIP5 and CMIP6 Models: Mean Biases, Future Projections, and Their Linkages. *J. Climate*, **33**, 6377–6398.

<https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-19-1029.1>

Manucharyan, G. E., & Thompson, A. F. (2022). Heavy footprints of upper-ocean eddies on weakened Arctic sea ice in marginal ice zones. *Nature communications*, 13(1), 2147.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-29663-0>

Manucharyan, G. E., & Thompson, A. F. (2017). Submesoscale sea ice-ocean interactions in marginal ice zones. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 122(12), 9455–9475.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JC012895>

Mariette, V., & Le Cann, B. (1985). Simulation of the formation of the Ushant thermal front. *Continental Shelf Research*, 4(6), 637–660.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0278-4343\(85\)90034-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0278-4343(85)90034-2)

Martinson, D. G. (1990). Evolution of the Southern Ocean winter mixed layer and sea ice: Open ocean deepwater formation and ventilation. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 95(C7), 11641–11654.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/JC095iC07p11641>

Mathiot, P., Jenkins, A., Harris, C., & Madec, G. (2017). Explicit representation and parameterized impacts of under ice shelf seas in the z coordinate ocean model NEMO 3.6. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 10(7), 2849–2874.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-10-2849-2017>

Maximenko, N. A., Bang, B., & Sasaki, H. (2005). Observational evidence of alternating zonal jets in the world ocean. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 32(12).

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2005GL022728>

Ménesguen, C., Delpech, A., Marin, F., Cravatte, S., Schopp, R., & Morel, Y. (2019). Observations and mechanisms for the formation of deep equatorial and tropical circulation. *Earth and Space Science*, 6(3), 370-386.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2018EA000438>

Ollitrault, M., & Verdère, A. C. de. (2014). The Ocean General Circulation near 1000-m Depth. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 44(1), 384–409. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-13-030.1>

Ollitrault, M., & Rannou, J.-P. (2013). ANDRO: An Argo-Based Deep Displacement Dataset. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 30(4), 759–788.

<https://doi.org/10.1175/JTECH-D-12-00073.1>

Ollitrault, M., Rannou, P., Brion, E., Cabanes, C., Piron, A., Reverdin, G., & Kolodziejczyk, N. (2024). ANDRO: An Argo-based deep displacement dataset [Dataset]. *SEANOE*.

<https://doi.org/10.17882/47077>

Palter, J. B. (2015). The Role of the Gulf Stream in European Climate. *Annual Review of Marine Science*, 7(Volume 7, 2015), 113–137.

<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-010814-015656>

Pujol, M.-I., Y. Faugère, G. Taburet, S. Dupuy, C. Pelloquin, M. Ablain, and N. Picot, 2016: DUACS DT2014: The new multi-mission altimeter data set reprocessed over 20 years. *Ocean Sci.*, **12**, 1067–1090.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/os-12-1067-2016>

Rackow, T., Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia, X., Becker, T., Milinski, S., Sandu, I., Aguridan, R., Bechtold, P., Beyer, S., Bidlot, J., Boussetta, S., Diamantakis, M., Dueben, P., Dutra, E., Forbes, R., Goessling, H. F., Hadade, I., Hegewald, J., Keeley, S., Kluft, L., ... Ziemen, F. (2024). Multi-year simulations at kilometre scale with the Integrated Forecasting System coupled to FESOM2.5/NEMOv3.4. *EGUsphere*, 2024, 1–59.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-913>

Raphael, M. N., Hobbs, W., & Wainer, I. (2011). The effect of Antarctic sea ice on the Southern Hemisphere atmosphere during the southern summer. *Climate Dynamics*, 36, 1403-1417.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-010-0892-1>

Rayner, N. A. A., Parker, D. E., Horton, E. B., Folland, C. K., Alexander, L. V., Rowell, D. P., ... & Kaplan, A. (2003). Global analyses of sea surface temperature, sea ice, and night marine air temperature since the late nineteenth century. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 108(D14).

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2002JD002670>

Rhines, P. B. (1975). Waves and turbulence on a beta-plane. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 69(3), 417-443.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112075001504>

Richards, K. J., Maximenko, N. A., Bryan, F. O., & Sasaki, H. (2006). Zonal jets in the Pacific Ocean. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 33(3).

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2005GL024645>

Roberts, C. D., Waters, J., Peterson, K. A., Palmer, M. D., McCarthy, G. D., Frajka-Williams, E., Haines, K., Lea, D. J., Martin, M. J., Storkey, D., Blockley, E. W., & Zuo, H. (2013). Atmosphere drives recent interannual variability of the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation at 26.5°N. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 40(19), 5164–5170.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/grl.50930>

Roberts, M. J., Baker, A., Blockley, E. W., Calvert, D., Coward, A., Hewitt, H. T., Jackson, L. C., Kuhlbrodt, T., Mathiot, P., Roberts, C. D., Schiemann, R., Seddon, J., Vannière, B., & Vidale, P. L. (2019). Description of the resolution hierarchy of the global coupled HadGEM3-GC3.1 model as used in CMIP6 HighResMIP experiments. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12(12), 4999–5028.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-4999-2019>

Roberts, M. J., Jackson, L. C., Roberts, C. D., Meccia, V., Docquier, D., Koenigk, T., Ortega, P., Moreno-Chamarro, E., Bellucci, A., Coward, A., Drijfhout, S., Exarchou, E., Gutjahr, O., Hewitt, H., Iovino, D., Lohmann, K., Putrasahan, D., Schiemann, R., Seddon, J., ... Wu, L. (2020). Sensitivity of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation to Model Resolution in CMIP6 HighResMIP Simulations and Implications for Future Changes. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 12(8), e2019MS002014.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2019MS002014>

Saba, V. S., Griffies, S. M., Anderson, W. G., Winton, M., Alexander, M. A., Delworth, T. L., Hare, J. A., Harrison, M. J., Rosati, A., Vecchi, G. A., & Zhang, R. (2016). Enhanced warming of the Northwest Atlantic Ocean under climate change. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 121(1), 118–132.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JC011346>

Sallée, J. B., Shuckburgh, E., Bruneau, N., Meijers, A. J., Bracegirdle, T. J., & Wang, Z. (2013). Assessment of Southern Ocean mixed-layer depths in CMIP5 models: Historical bias and forcing response. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 118(4), 1845-1862.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrc.20157>

Schoonover, J., Dewar, W., Wienders, N., Gula, J., McWilliams, J. C., Molemaker, M. J., Bates, S. C., Danabasoglu, G., & Yeager, S. (2016). North Atlantic Barotropic Vorticity Balances in Numerical Models. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 46(1), 289–303.

<https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-15-0133.1>

Sein, D. V., Koldunov, N. V., Danilov, S., Sidorenko, D., Wekerle, C., Cabos, W., Rackow, T., Scholz, P., Semmler, T., Wang, Q., & Jung, T. (2018). The Relative Influence of Atmospheric and Oceanic Model Resolution on the Circulation of the North Atlantic Ocean in a Coupled Climate Model. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 10(8), 2026–2041.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2018MS001327>

Si, W., Liu, H., & Zhang, M. (2023). Ocean Dynamics Causes the Equatorial Pacific SST Bias in CAS-ESM2-0. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 128(22), e2023JD039593.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2023JD039593>

Taguchi, B., Xie, S.-P., Schneider, N., Nonaka, M., Sasaki, H., & Sasai, Y. (2007). Decadal Variability of the Kuroshio Extension: Observations and an Eddy-Resolving Model Hindcast. *Journal of Climate*, 20(11), 2357–2377.

<https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI4142.1>

Talley, L. D., Pickard, G. L., Emery, W. J., & Swift, J. H. (2011a). Chapter 9—Atlantic Ocean. In L. D. Talley, G. L. Pickard, W. J. Emery, & J. H. Swift (Eds.), *Descriptive Physical Oceanography* (Sixth Edition) (pp. 245–301). Academic Press.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-7506-4552-2.10009-5>

Talley, L. D., Pickard, G. L., Emery, W. J., & Swift, J. H. (2011b). Chapter 12—Arctic Ocean and Nordic Seas. In L. D. Talley, G. L. Pickard, W. J. Emery, & J. H. Swift (Eds.), *Descriptive Physical Oceanography* (Sixth Edition) (pp. 401–436). Academic Press.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-7506-4552-2.10012-5>

Terray, L., L. Corre, S. Cravatte, T. Delcroix, G. Reverdin, and A. Ribes, 2012: Near-Surface Salinity as Nature's Rain Gauge to Detect Human Influence on the Tropical Water Cycle. *J. Climate*, 25, 958–977,

<https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-10-05025.1>

Tréguier, A.M., Deshayes, J., Le Sommer, J., Lique, C., Madec, G., Penduff, T., Molines, J.-M., Barnier, B., Bourdalle-Badie, R. and Talandier, C. (2014). Meridional transport of salt in the global ocean from an eddy-resolving model. *Ocean Sci.*, 10, 243-255, 2014

<https://os.copernicus.org/articles/10/243/2014/>

Tréguier, A M., de Boyer Montégut, C., Bozec, A., Chassignet, E. P., Fox-Kemper, B., McC. Hogg, A., ... & Yeager, S. (2023). The mixed-layer depth in the Ocean Model Intercomparison Project (OMIP): impact of resolving mesoscale eddies. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 16(13), 3849-3872.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-3849-2023, 2023.>

Trenberth, K. E., 1997: The Definition of El Niño. *Bulletin of American Meteorology Society*, 78, 2771–2778.

[https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477\(1997\)078<2771:TDOENO>2.0.CO;2.](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477(1997)078<2771:TDOENO>2.0.CO;2.)

Trenberth, K. E., & Fasullo, J. T. (2017). Atlantic meridional heat transports computed from balancing Earth's energy locally. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 44(4), 1919–1927.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/2016GL072475>

van Sebille, E., Kamenkovich, I., & Willis, J. K. (2011). Quasi-zonal jets in 3-D Argo data of the northeast Atlantic. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 38(2).

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2010GL046267>

Wang, Q., & Pierini, S. (2020). On the Role of the Kuroshio Extension Bimodality in Modulating the Surface Eddy Kinetic Energy Seasonal Variability. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 47(3), e2019GL086308.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GL086308>

Wang, S., Wang, Q., Wang, M., Lohmann, G., & Qiao, F. (2022). Arctic Ocean freshwater in CMIP6 coupled models. *Earth's Future*, 10, e2022EF002878.

<https://doi.org/10.1029/2022EF002878>

Wang, Y., Heywood, K. J., Stevens, D. P., & Damerell, G. M. (2022). Seasonal extrema of sea surface temperature in CMIP6 models. *Ocean Science*, 18(3), 839–855.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/os-18-839-2022>

Xavier, P., Willett, M., Graham, T., Earnshaw, P., Copsey, D., Narayan, N., Marzin, C., Sellar, A., Ackerley, D., Blockley, E., Bodas-Salcedo, A., Bushell, A., Chua, X. R., Guiavarc'h, C., Hassim, M., Heming, J., Hudson, D., Ineson, S., Jones, C., Keane, R., Kuhlbrodt, T., Martin, G., McCabe, A., Ridley, J., Roberts, L., Schiemann, R., Storkey, D., Tennant, W., Tomassini, L., Tsushima, Y., West, A., Wheeler, M., Zhu, H., Blaker, A. T., Jones, A., Megann, A., Regayre, L., and Williams, K. (2024). GC5 documentation paper, *in preparation*.

Zalesak, S. T. (1979). Fully multidimensional flux-corrected transport algorithms for fluids. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 31(3), 335–362.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991\(79\)90051-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991(79)90051-2)

Zhang, J., & Rothrock, D. A. (2003). Modeling global sea ice with a thickness and enthalpy distribution model in generalized curvilinear coordinates. *Monthly Weather Review*, 131(5), 845–861.

[https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(2003\)131%3C0845:MGSIWA%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(2003)131%3C0845:MGSIWA%3E2.0.CO;2)